

MASTER'S DEGREE IN INTERNATIONAL AND COMPARATIVE
EDUCATION

THE PROGRESSING MACHINE OR LEARNING AS THE
ART OF THE *RIGHT MEASURE*

(A Study Within a Humanistic and Philosophic Framework)

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The man
Of virtuous soul commands not nor obeys.
Power like a desolating pestilence
Pollutes whate'er it touches: and obedience,
Bane of all genius, virtue, freedom, truth,
Makes slaves of men, and of the human frame
A mechanized automaton.

Shelley

ABSTRACT

This study is a long reflection, within a philosophical and humanistic tradition, about some mechanistic structures that seem to be the ridgepoles our society, and the main contributors for the engineering of subjects of this same society. These mechanistic structures, of which Education is part, are in our opinion, obeying to essentially rigid, isomorphic and mechanic laws, which clearly represent an inadequate perception of the dynamics implicit in each context, each situation, each environment *as it is*. These structures are what we call a *progressing machine* that is being globalised under various pretexts, namely education, development, modernity, etc. However, being a machine, its responses to challenge are restricted to a limited set of possibilities, whereas reality's challenges demand much more than that as a response.

In our opinion this systematic failure that is either felt or suspected both on a macro-scale, by countries and nations; or in a micro-scale, by the individuals, in bringing about such development, such education, is result of that inadequate and mainly mechanistic response that is being given to the multiple and interrelated challenges that our times present. Within this work we argue that what is clearly amiss both in society, in general, and in education, in particular, is a creative response as opposed to a mechanistic one. A response that represents *something else* beyond the pre-established set of possible responses. A creative response with the quality and nature of art itself. The art of the *right measure*.

Descriptors: | Progressive machine, human-scale, system, structure, development, globalisation, education, iron law of oligarchy, colonialism, individuals/subjects, engineering, consumerism, self, taxonomy, repetition/routine, passivity, boredom, transgression, alienation, addiction, nomad spirit, right measure/contemplation, learning, relevance, adequacy, art, creativity, turning point, change, flux, chaos, holism.

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1. CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION AND STRUCTURAL MOTIVATION

We are living in a very strange world, where there is no space to live freely. One of the most precious things that we have is the possibility of being alone and reflect about life, because this is one of the few things in which no one superior has authority. I think that I do not know myself completely, and it will take some time until that happens. Maybe I should try to know myself better, but the society where I live does not allow that. This because our society has habits and routines that need urgent change, otherwise many people will die without knowing themselves. More and more people are losing the joy for life because they cannot free themselves from those habits — but how could they, if nowadays society does not permit it? Why should there be an authority in everything people do? I think that in order to be able to know ourselves we should act by ourselves and not under command. (...)” (Joana Silva 8th grade, fifteen year-old student from the Secondary School Rainha D. Leonor, Lisboa.)¹

This dissertation is, in itself, a moment in our own on-going process of learning. In this sense this dissertation, itself, can be considered a *walk*, a work that wanders in free territory, in the no-man’s land of philosophy — where one has freedom to put all questions and find improbable answers. When we use the term *philosophy* we mean by that the original spirit which throughout ages motivated people to put questions. Most of these impossible questions. Philosophy means the inquisitive passion for the events of life and the underlying force ordering them. The word philosophy itself has in its root this meaning — the passion for the indefinable. So in order to write this dissertation we decided to *reflect* about life, avoiding to the utmost having any sort of previous conclusions, or authoritative landmarks to pre-define the path to be taken in this travel. Only when entering the territory of the unknown can something new be found. This newness is what can be understood as learning. So, we are, in an active

¹ Excerpt, under the title “Know Yourself”, extracted from school’s poetry magazine *Morpheu*, n. 4, May 2000. (Our translation).

present, learning while writing this work — and not simply reproducing the already known.

Some points seem to us of crucial importance in an investigation and the learning that springs from it. These points are like inter-flowing moments of a process that we consider important to live while writing and doing investigation. These points can, roughly, be described as

- 1) Allowing the driving force of questioning to bloom, i.e., to have total awareness in oneself of the immense curiosity and will to discover, regarding life as a whole. In this moment of the process...
- 2) ...any sort of questioning is diffuse, and the implications of questions are immense. The pre-history of any question is like a sensual intuition, a hunch². Regarding such a hunch, such vague questioning (it is more like a *feeling* than an conceptualisation) it is important...
- 3) ...to let the inquisitive mind observe the surrounding events reflectively, like a mirror, thus avoiding distortion caused by previous knowledge. Attention is understood as a non theory-laden³ pristine intensity.
- 4) Previous knowledge, and references (like authors, theories, etc.) have to come into use only when relevant, as tools that help to formalise, to represent what has been felt and observed.

The authors and theories (theory in the original Greek sense, having a common root with the word “theatre”, meaning view, and *insight* into reality, not being in itself *the*

² See Structural Questions for clarification of this word.

³ It is interesting to take into consideration the position that states that it is impossible to observe without having any theoretical assumptions. This leads to the doctrine of *Incommensurability* (with no measure): different observations imply different theories, thus different observers with different theories inhabit different worlds. This is a sort of *post-modern fragmentation* mixed with *idealism*, in the sense that is considered that the world *is* what we think of it.

reality, but *a representation*) are to be used as pointers of directions, like windsocks show the direction of the wind, not being themselves the wind, though there is a relationship between them. In the same way our intention with this dissertation is to raise some questions, not aiming at giving answers or solutions. (If ancient philosophers were only to talk when able to provide solutions to their questions and criticisms, philosophy would have never been born). Actually, one of the fundamental points of this dissertation is the question that the prescription of solutions and blueprints is one of the main reasons why 1) passivity is so propagated; 2) the ability of learning is impeded and 3) original solutions are not discovered — be it by nations in general, or individuals in particular. Consequently we do not want to bring about conclusions, but to raise questions, point directions that lead to dialogue and mutual learning.

1.2 STRUCTURAL QUESTIONS

This dissertation had as motivation an intuition, a feeling or hunch. Both as student, and then as high-school teacher there was, in our opinion, a recurrent and persistent feeling that something was seriously inadequate in the whole educational context and its relation with society. Some of the basic symptoms of such ill being in the educational context were visible in the too frequent outbursts of conflict that top a ground of long lasting passivity. Both between people, and within the individual, the school seemed a place of strife and inner apathy. Being aware, as teacher, of the incredible curiosity that young people have, it seemed to us that a great deal of waste is going on in the education of innumerable youngsters, specially considering the reduced effects this same education seems to have⁴:

⁴ We assume a (non-radical) pessimistic posture regarding the present state of humans, both in their relation with environment, society and themselves as individuals — which does not mean that we do not consider the possibility for a change as something within reach.

On the one hand, our world, as an organic system, needs an urgent change in our approach to it — is education laying the foundations for a totally new relationship with it? On the other, the individual needs totally new directions *pointed out* to him⁵ in order to walk a new path⁶, and make new discoveries — is education rich and broad enough to open up new horizons?

Consequently some questions will be considered structural in this dissertation, namely:

- Is there a *progressive machine* being globalised — engineering the world into an isomorphic system (under the clench of an iron law of oligarchy)⁷ where people are to be considered as objectified masses of consumerists?
- Is Education reproducing the same general tendency, being itself a standardised product to be sold — being something, in most cases, inadequate, essentially the same here, there and everywhere? (What relation has that with its taxonomic⁸, compulsive and curricular characteristics?)
- What are the general features and structures of this Education, if we consider it to reproduce the general tendencies of our consumerist society? (Basically, what is meant by Education when such a term is being used?).
- Is this Education real *learning*? (Implying discovery, freedom — bringing new insight into the crucial problems of our reality, such as violence, waste, or inner emptiness).
- What is *learning*?

1.3. METHODOLOGY

⁵ For convenience we will not use her/him, she/he, etc. We will choose to use the masculine form exclusively on the ground that it matches the researcher's own gender.

⁶ The pointing out of directions implies that one new possibility, one new way can be shown — however, the walking has to be done by the individual himself.

⁷ Detailed discussion on this term in note 32

⁸ Taxonomy related to the systematic classification, division into classes, examination, selection, hierarchy, categorisation, and space-time allocation.

The questions that are raised in this thesis are extremely broad, but it is our conviction that a correct investigation and approach should start from the general to the particular. Reality is a whole and not a collection of fragments — in such a manner beginning an approach from the most general is in closer relation to reality than solely concentrating ones' sight on one point. The questions raised will lead, along the chapters, to more detailed propositions that, themselves are points of debate and dialogue. These propositions will be seen as sub-interrogation marks inside a more general and bigger question mark. So, nothing in this work is to be seen as an assertive statement. In questions such as “what is learning?” some propositions will be given, but we emphasise the importance of taking them solely as provisory pointers of other possibilities, which means that any attempt to make any sort of definitive definition is totally against the spirit of this work.

Considering what was said in the previous paragraph in relation to a general approach to the topic, it should be added that, to some extent, we avoided just using exclusively typical educational bibliography and authors, but decided to use many other sources as well. The reason is simple: each field of knowledge is pervaded by an intrinsic logic and discourse. Due to the fact that that logic, or epistemology, ends up *making sense* for one when reading it — it is very easy to fall into the trap of just considering the problems, and seeing the questions from that specific point of view. A point of view with its own structure, terminology and jargon. As the artist C. Biederman puts it, in order to have insight into a question and being able to perceive the inner order in it, one has to “give attention to similar differences and different similarities”⁹. By this we mean that we find it much more fruitful to approach, say, an educational issue using as tool theories from other fields, than immersing in an already settled, self-related, self-consistent corpus of discourse and logic. Using, for example, as one of our primary sources of inspiration and pointer the quantum theory scientist Bohm, or the Greek philosopher Heraclitus, we are trying to mirror the differences — which means, to “give attention to similar differences and different similarities” — that, across the artificially fragmented fields of knowledge, are recurrent as fluid patterns; i.e., at different levels and in different areas of reality, one thing mirrors all other things,

⁹ On C. Biederman: *Art as the Evolution of Visual Knowledge*, Red Wing, Minnesota, 1948

as if there were a presence of everything in everything¹⁰. In this sense, there are great lessons to be learned, parallels that can be drawn, and realities that can be mirrored regarding Education (or anything else), from watching the wave formations in the ocean; from studying the fractal order behind the chaos theory; the remaining sentences of Heraclitus, or the non-causal interaction of wave movements in quantum experiments.

1. 4. TERMINOLOGY AND A SHARED MEANING

Due to the inter-disciplinary implications that this kind of approach has, it is necessary to make a continuous clarification of terms and words as the work proceeds. One of our main concerns has been the question of how to avoid a fragmentation of meanings. Presently, due to a fragmentation of the field of knowledge into a myriad of linguistically hermetic disciplines, the same words acquire different meanings, and evoke different associations and responses in the listener/reader. Consequently, we considered as one of our fundamental tools the use of several dictionaries, (some of these being *The Penguin Dictionary of Philosophy*, edit. Mautner, T.; *Collins Dictionary of Sociology*, edit. Jary, D.; Jary, J.; assoc. edit. Nicholls, P.; Sillitoe, A.; *The Blackwell Dictionary of Sociology*, edit. Johnson, A.J.; *Longman Dictionary of English Language and Culture*; etc). And also, our background studies in Philosophy, Latin, Classic Culture, Linguistics, Syntax and Semantics, etc., that were precious in such a task of clarifying what was related with terms, definitions and words.

Trying to find definitions for the words, so that they share a common meaning for all involved in the dialogue that this dissertation proposes, is not an easy task. One single word, like *system* or *development*, can cause a great deal of confusion and interference in the process of communication if the meaning is not clarified. But it is not just the more structural, “archaeological”¹¹, encyclopaedic meaning of the word that

¹⁰ “To see the world in a grain of sand
And a Heaven in a Wild Flower
Hold Infinity in the palm of your hand
And Eternity in an hour”. (Blake: 1972: 431)

¹¹ A good understanding and clarification of words can be done by some sort of archaeological investigation into the past meaning of words. Taking, for instance, the word *intelligence*: this word is formed by two other Latin words *inter* and *legere* — meaning, “to read between”. Intelligence is, thus,

is problematic. Comparably, much more complex and difficult is the use of words and concepts of which, unconsciously, we take a shared meaning for granted. For example, if we use the word *development* or *progress*, what are we in fact meaning? Erroneously we consider that these words are self-evident in their meaning. Easily one can say that development is fundamental — because the semantics of the word brings up a vague cluster of meanings associated with something “good” — but what is, in fact, and according to whom, development, progress? “For general well being, being educated is good, necessary” — this is something that can be uttered with the same ease and self-confidence as something such as “for general well-being, being healthy is good, necessary.” But while physically it is easier to establish what well being is, culturally it becomes very complex. “Education is good” — but which education? A Spartan, a Swedish, a Zen one?

Some of the concepts that will demand special care as we proceed are, for instance, development, progress, education, learning, potential, system, structure, mechanism, etc.

1.5. LIMITATIONS

The main limitation of this work is related with our own background and academic tradition. In this sense this means that this work will be mostly within a philosophical and humanistic tradition. This because our objective is to put questions, in a philosophical and humanistic manner, and take their implications as far and deep as possible. In this sense, more than proving, taxonomically, a point to the reader, we prefer the reader’s willingness to hear, to feel empathy with the problematic that we are pointing at — and, thus, join us in our journey.

the *reading between the lines*. Intelligence is the understanding, the *insight* and ability that goes beyond the lines of information, reading the implicit and subtle meanings in between these lines. Another interesting word is *individual*, which comes from the word *individuum*, the Latin translation of *atomon*. In this sense, the primary meaning of individual would signify undividedness, non-fragmentation. The individual means something whole, integral, not constituted by the sum of bundled pieces or fragments. Further ahead in this thesis the explanation given in this footnote will become of crucial importance.

Another limitation is related with the articulated nature of the work. In this work is not enough just to read the introduction and conclusion, in order to get the marrow of it. It is impossible to make it into a nutshell. In fact, this work is a process in itself, demanding the reader to go through a process as well. The work, in any stage, has implicit all the others stages, mirroring and paralleling them. Each point of the work is interdependent and supporting another. This means that, to get an overall picture of the work, one has to go through the pains of reading the whole of it.

One other limitation is the number and extension of our footnotes. Although they are not seen as a problem in most academic circles, we, nevertheless, went through a great deal of trouble in order to try to solve this question. We did not succeed. And the reason is because such footnotes are clarifications that we consider opportune to be given in *that* particular stage of the reading process. They should, then, be in the same page. Thus, it would make no sense putting them either in the beginning or in the end, or elsewhere.

2. CHAPTER TWO: A MACHINE BEYOND THE HUMAN SCALE

2.1. FIRST AND SECOND SET OF PROPOSITIONS: A SPECIFIC GLOBALISATION, DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION AS COGS OF A BIG MACHINE?

When writing about important issues such as education, development and the appalling brutality that rules in our present world, one has to be both cautious and humble. In the present chapter we will attempt to do a critical examination of several issues, an examination which should be regarded as a challenge, as a friendly invitation to dialogue.

There is no doubt, at least between people of good will, that education, development and aid are fundamental necessities in our world. Nevertheless, it is not the discussion of the unquestionable nature of these points that make us write about the present questions. Definitely education, development and aid are crucial. But, the question is: *what kind of education, development and aid?*

The investigation that will be attempted is towards an examining of what is meant when such terms are used. And, also, what legitimacy and validity they might have when what is observed in our own contemporary history is somehow a repetition, an eternal return, of old patterns of ignorance and violence. Besides we consider that under the name of development, globalisation and education, a dangerous mechanistic structure is being spread over the globe. And in order to begin the examination of this same statement we will advance two sets of propositions. First set of propositions:

- Development seen as a branch of a *specific globalisation*¹² process.
- A *specific globalisation* seen as a new form of colonialism.
- Development, in this specific sense, seen as a new form of colonialism.

Second set of propositions:

- Institutions and big mechanistic structures or systems¹³ (corporations, conglomerates, etc.) tend to isomorphism, corruption and senility.

¹² Firstly, the term *Globalisation* is a very problematic one. Nevertheless, it should be made very clear, that in our approach to this theme, we are definitely in favour of a *Globalisation* of, say, environmental responsibility, Human Rights, cultural richness and scientific knowledge that contributes for general well-being, etc. In this sense, we could propose the ethic posture and concept of *Humanistic Universalism*, as a substitute of the so beaten-up term Globalisation. We use *Humanism* in the sense of a “full development of the individual, rejecting religious asceticism, narrow scholasticism (...)”. *Humanism* understood as a non-religious “world-view, usually based on a belief in man’s capacity for self-cultivation (...); man as an autonomous being, capable of self-determination, together with the assumption that an individual’s choices can make a real difference to a society (...)” (Mautner: 2000:256). And we use *Universalism* according to the view that “all human beings are morally equally in the sense that membership of a certain tribe, class, caste, nation, race, etc. as such neither justifies special consideration nor excuses lack of consideration”. (Mautner: 2000: 479,80). Secondly, when we are doing a critical analysis of globalisation, we are mainly concerned with two gigantic multinationals — namely Violence and Stupidity. “Multinationals” to which belong too many people, including, those who *violently fight against* multinationals and *globalisation*.

¹³ This will be an important set of ideas throughout our dissertation. We will make a contrast between *mechanic structures and systems* and *creative structures and systems*. In the case of the first ones, it is clear that we are dealing with something that represents a repetitive, limited interplay of organised and superficially related elements — like the interacting, but separated, pieces of an engine. And that, like the kaleidoscope, cannot, fundamentally, create, just rearrange what was previously already present. The second ones will represent the qualities of the living organism, being an essentially dynamic and harmonic inter-relation and adaptation, which has room for creativity. (In the last chapter there will be a link done between these creative structures and art and music. Art and music which are, themselves, a creative and flowing order, or structure, or system). On a slightly different approach, if we were, for example, to consider thought as a *mechanical* process or system (basically triggered by memory), then we could say that intelligence would represent a *creative* perception that brings new understanding, insight

- A specific globalisation process is mainly being driven and implemented by means of enormous institutions, corporations and structures.
- Such a globalisation process (and together with it, development and education) brought about through these means leads to isomorphism, corruption and senility.

2.2. THE PROMISE OF MODERNISATION, THE CONTEMPORARY EL DORADO

As a threat at the basis of the present concept of democracy, is the fact that in our own societies the proportion of people who are voting is declining. This reduced voting reveals the decrease of representation that people feel in contemporary politics. Politicians are in too many cases seen as lazy and corrupt, and the power is felt to be elsewhere. The power is not with them anymore¹⁴. This can be seen, for example, in the fact that the protests lately in European and American cities were not directed towards the usual "White Houses", but towards seemingly obscure entities that until the moment, very few recognised as centres of power, such as economic organisations or multinationals (Boaventura: 2001: 19).

It is, thus, felt that forms of economic power and control are the ruling powers nowadays. (Economics is the new ruling religion, and this means power over technology, information and mass culture/education) (Odora: 1989: Chapters 7 & 8). Nowadays power is not represented by ideologies, but is situated within that which in

into the whole process. (The relieving mental *a-ha!* that one *suddenly* utters when, *suddenly*, an intricate problem is solved – as if *by itself*). Intelligence would represent the ability to discover a deeper order implicit *between the lines* of thought. Therefore, and as we referred in footnote 12 about intelligence, one can say, that intelligence or creativity are a non-mechanistic response. This because they are “the inception of new content, which unfolds into a sequence of moments that is not completely derivable from what came earlier in this sequence or set of such sequences.” (Bhom: 1980: 50)

¹⁴ In fact most people who say that they are *against* globalisation do not have a clue as to what both globalisation or anti-globalisation mean. Their *being against* is much more the result of a feeling of suspicion about the existence of things and decisions that do not depend on their opinion or knowledge in order to exist or to be taken. These things being big structures of great and concentrated power — which have the capacity to act regardless of people’s opinion or knowledge. Democracy is, thus, endangered when a sense of *distance* is felt between the power and the citizens — the general “*public*”, the spectators (Dahrendorf: 2001: 5).

this thesis, will be called big institutions or corporations (Dahrendorf: 2001: 5). (We remind the reader that the point of this paper *is not* to make a critique of institutions *in themselves*, but to use the discussion of their symbolic — and real — power as means to clarify other points. So, it should be repeated that this is not an institutional analysis thesis, rather a philosophical one. However, in order to be more specific, it can be advanced that when one is referring to "big organisations" and "institutions" one is referring to big structured organisations and institutions like the Bretton Wood ones, Aid related Agencies, transnational corporations, and Governments in general).

Together with this economic power, that nowadays can be called neo-liberalism, runs a globalisation process, the construction of what London Financial Times, James Morgan calls the "de facto world government" or what Meyer and Ramirez describe as a world-society or system (Mayer, Ramirez; 1997:144). There is a specific globalisation process going on — but not necessarily a democratic one (Boaventura: 2001: 19)¹⁵. This can be understood in the following light: certain globalisation processes and procedures do not, necessarily, mean processes towards a more democratic and equitable world (Bello&Cunningham: 1994: 1). Quite the opposite, due to the Structural Adjustment Policies (SAPs) and other measures characteristic of such globalisation process, polarisation was increased (Odora: 1998: 1). Poverty in the Third World has not diminished but the opposite has happened (Schwab: 2001: 30). "The programs dictated by the International Monetary Fund and World Bank, have helped to double the gap between rich and poor countries since 1960". (Chomsky, 1993: 1)

Of course all the information that nowadays is produced for the masses is surrounded by a haze of propaganda and near-truths (As Papini says, the greatest lie is the one that only very slightly deviates from the truth). Information makes for a present homogeneity of truth and perception of reality. Everything that the channels of information spread is seen as the truth. They are unanimous — one voice, one version.. With information and media, themselves, controlled by monopolies, it is very hard to know what is the truth nowadays, and "citizens not only do not intrude into the public arena but scarcely have an idea of the policies that will shape their lives" (Chomsky;

¹⁵ The four Asian Tigers are a good example of that.

1993:2). Technology and economic domination lead to a rhetoric of domination. All big companies end up being owned by a few and same individuals¹⁶.

It is difficult to tell the truth from the false. Recognising the false as false is the greatest art of our times. And this also applies to the information given by the big institutions dealing with education, the case in which we are particularly interested. To start with, on a purely academic level of text and discourse analysis, one can observe that the writing style of most of these organisations is palimpsestic, redundant and opaque. There is a great quantity of informational noise that either confuses or simply dissuades the reader to take the pains to read through it. Maybe because this type of documents is "clearly the result of a series of compromises" (Samoff: 1996:2). This informational confusion is not only an issue in the case of the average citizen that wants to be informed — in fact this goes all the way up to politicians that sign educational documents, out of a superficial understanding. Superficial understanding provided by the briefings and *précis* handed out by their "hermeneutical staff", between two meetings or two meals.

The point that is being made here is that there are big decisions being taken based on little knowledge, and according to the interests of a very few big institutions. Besides, with the power seen as an economic power situated within corporations, one can ask to what extent the democratic representation is in fact a reality, "if the important decisions that affect peoples' lives no more correspond to institutions that they can control" (Dahrendorf: 2001: 5)¹⁷.

These big institutions, of which so few seem to know the real nature and purposes, are the ones that present themselves as the "guardians of the world's

¹⁶ In Portugal, for example, a few Citizen Kane replicas are, themselves, owners of newspapers, magazines, Television channels, Internet gateways, art collections, etc.

¹⁷ In this same article Ralph Dahrendorf (British sociologist, ex-director of the London School of Economics and present member of the House of the Lords) points to another important issue. The fact that there is a legitimate feeling of uneasiness regarding the actual state of our money-directed society, this does not legitimate fundamentalist attacks, enraged reactions against this same society. In fact, the inadequate and delusional nostalgia for a pre-modern society can be extremely dangerous and disastrous, as the Nazi ideology has already proved (Dahrendorf: 2001: 5). For us it is obvious, that it is not through the destructive attack of the present society that an intelligent action can be brought into being — even if we were to be transplanted to a pre-modern society we would still carry, within ourselves, the same questions, the same past, the same unsolved problems. Problems that only can be solved here and now. Not elsewhere.

wisdom”, and “protectors of the poor and disadvantaged of the world - they are the ones who bring the solutions”. (Samoff, 2001: SIDA & IIE)¹⁸. At a cost, of course.

However, the solutions that the affluent countries present for the world crisis are, themselves, born out of the system that also contributed to this crisis in the first place. These developing, modernising, civilising solutions are sprung out of a system — that in itself — is engineered *not* to contemplate the general good. The affluent countries sell a model of life as the world's panacea for injustice, poverty and exploitation; a model which, in fact, is the cause why these maladies — that the system is promising to cure — exist. This is to say that this model has existence thanks to the evils that it is promising to cure. In the end only the promise remains.

The system that promises the modern El Dorado for all is, inherently, a system that in order to keep itself functional, must maintain most of humans excluded — otherwise this system would collapse. The modern El Dorado is for a few, but the promise of it is for all (Fuller, 1991: ix). And it is the promise that has to continue being sold, because it is this same promise that allows the system to continue exploring and draining most of the world's population of its resources and wealth.

In order to fulfil its verbal and ideal promise of *growing up modern*, (which means concretising the picture of modernity as we know it in the affluent countries, *with its commodities, expenditures and consumerism*) on a global scale, the system would have to commit a sort of self-destruction, because the resources are limited. Achieving the promise and allowing the whole world to live according to the model and standard of the "developed" societies would probably mean universal hunger after a short while.

The researcher is giving attention to this point because this promise of modernisation has Education as one of its main discourse keywords. The spreading of the educational system, as we know it, is the promise for an El Dorado of Modernity. A present system, which is both compulsory and selective — that is *both and simultaneously* 1) the promise of a key to knowledge and wisdom, and 2) the same old repetitive, limited, curricular system and concept of education. And this system is to be the same here and there, and everywhere. Education is seen not as a growing process, as

¹⁸ Course given by Joel Samoff at SIDA, April 2001

a pathless land, a land in which each individual is a pioneer, but a concrete, quantifiable goal that can be measured in the scale of "modernity". Modernity, which in reality, is not to be attained by the whole.

Absolute priorities and austere simplicity should be regarded possibilities in order to bring about a development of the whole — a global development. Thus could the human society start sharing what *there is* to be shared. The promise of sharing what is not there to be shared seems futile and perverse. Perverse in the sense that this promise is itself a purchasable product and the buying of this promise has its price. And this price is extremely high. It means the importation of foreign formulas, — and an alien form of education that means a form of acculturation, because, and this is interesting to observe, more and more there is a connection being made between the concept of "education" and "culture". So, an imported education, is an imported culture.

2.3. SCHOOLS AND TECHNOLOGY, THE TWO FACES OF JANUS

All the international aid given by the affluent world, by creating schools, seems not to be relevant in its consequences and results. It can be argued that this aid ends up trying to tackle problems and needs that were not initially present — problems and needs that are created by those who, now, try to help and solve them (Ilich: 1971: 3). Schools became one more problem to solve, one more problem that needs to be helped.

Creating need for a specific type of education makes demand match the offer and vice-versa. The provider, that has only **X** to sell, creates the need for this same **X** in the recipient - when the recipient starts to demand **X** the provider is ready to fulfil the need. This is a simple strategy of market. Education and learning are, thus, associated with *one specific form* of education and learning, which is the one proposed by the big institutions of the affluent countries. But the fact that this *one* type of education, *one* concept of education, has possibly been effective (which is very arguable) in the place from where it came — does not guarantee the same result in the next. But it is the faith in this one system, and its promise that keeps it going on. And

Such faith in the role of the school is not limited to these Western nations, however. It has been exported, along with its rationalising and "modern" tendencies and techniques, throughout the world. In Africa, Asia, and Latin America, governments turn to the Western school to develop paths of opportunity and to enable their children to "grow up modern". In what is called the "Third World", however, mass schooling is not delivering on its promises. In fact, this may understate the problem dramatically. (Fuller; 1991:xi)

Nevertheless, the people of the Third World having bought the myth, the promise and the faith in this *one* specific education, dependency is created, and this "renders them increasingly incapable of organising their own lives around their own experiences and resources within their own communities" (Ilich; 1971:4). Regarding, then, people's choice in education — the saying and opinion that the people, from the places whereto this education has been transplanted, have about these crucial issues — such freedom is restricted to choices between further reforms and restructuring, between different combinations of the same thing, which is as futile and illusive as the freedom of choosing between Coca-Cola and Pepsi — it is just more of the same thing. More institutionalised learning shaped according to big organisations.

Attached to the logic of progress, comes, obviously technology¹⁹. The technological progress brought about the machine, nuclear bomb and an increasing life

¹⁹ A deep observation of the actual technological *speeding machine* would reveal many more implications and aspects than what one would expect. The incredible technological boost of our present days, has connections to a psychological level of urges, desires and dreams that are far more interesting than what one would at first suppose. Therefore, we consider it interesting to make a few comments regarding our present technological revolution. This, because our technological revolution is not just about faster computers and smarter machines. Actually, the present "cyberdelic culture" (Dery: 1996: 21-72) holds within a promise, a faith, for the solution of an old ennui, the longing of returning to the original Matrix (or metaverso, as Stephenson, 1993, calls it) and the paradoxical projection of it in the future. An impossible tomorrow to be attained as soon as possible. The underlying *topos* which are most recurrent in this cyberdelic culture are: symbiosis of human/machine; alteration of sensorial and psychic experience through electric, mechanic and chemical means; digital simulation and stimulation, which will become the new Reality for the new technological man. And, undoubtedly one of the fulcra of the cyberdelic culture is the relation of the person with the body. The ancestral Jew-Christian duality mind/body, that dialectic with no conciliation, is, in this new culture, extreme. In our cyberdelic culture the body is made *thing*, objectified, made raw material to be moulded, emptied, amplified and augmented (as clay for the future *golem*). Within this body will be found the mind, a mind that has access to the matrix — a mind that can, unsubstantial and endowed with preternatural qualities, blend in static ecstasy with the *deus-in-machina*. The mind melts, in, a truly digital *parousia*, inside the anachronic and utopic cyberspace, where, it can finally get rid of the burdening flesh. However, for defence and sophistication of this mind's performance it is argued that the body has to be transformed, re-designed, re-structured with technological detachment and skill. Consequently, at a deep level, an amplification of a sense implies an

span. The latter without, however and unfortunately, bettering the quality of life of most of the people in the globe — just prolonging it. Neither war nor plundering were understood and eradicated from human reality, so technology that was expected to become the world's *Paraklitos*²⁰ ended up becoming a problem itself. After so much progress, humans are still human's worse enemies — *homo homini lupus* — man is the wolf of man. And the Malthusian predictions continue gloomily valid in an overpopulating world, where war and disease still claim their toll. Regarding technology as a means to better human reality is another form of illusion. It *could* have, obviously, helped — but the fact is that in most cases it just serves to 1) prolong the power struggles (there is a tendency either to make of technological advances a mechanism of control, or a by-pass control device) and 2) to produce more of what is not, fundamentally, needed — this for consumerism reasons. Instead of fulfilling its own promise technology also brings further complexity and widens the gap between societies.

Regarding the fact that its spreading *in* and *together* with schools is promoted, there are a few comments that should be made. The first is that hardware is driven by software. Affluent countries' software is continuously two steps ahead of the one catch-up step given by the Third World. This ends up creating a continuous demand of software — and consequently a hardware substitution. The commercial logic behind this process is not difficult to follow. The catch-up cannot ever catch-up. But the spending and dependency are continuous. The second is that good learning, good

anaesthetising of this same sense (Dery: 1996: 164). This sense accommodates more information, but fundamentally *feels less*. The artificial amplification — the penetration caused by technology — is a violence against which, at a structural level, the entity (body-mind, in its whole) reacts, self-desensitising itself. The human being has to numb, anaesthetise himself in order to be exposed and amplified — otherwise it is destroyed (Dery: 1996: 160-8). The body has to be *estranged* from itself — made passive in relation to the anxiety of the mind. Then, this “docile body” can be “subjected, used, transformed and improved” (Foucault: 1977: 136). The cyberdelic culture, that grows by the hour, is the step ahead in that Darwinian process of selection, evolution and alteration (defended, for example, in the past, by Marinetti, or presently, by Sterlac: “The body not as a subject but as an object — NOT AS AN OBJECT OF DESIRING BUT AS AN OBJECT FOR DESIGNING” (Dery: 1996: 161). The human being, altering the way *how* he feels — altering his perception — necessarily is altered in his way of being. When the way reality is perceived is altered, then the one who perceives it, is also altered. The body made object, disconnected from itself and reconnected to reality (in fact, to the machine) by technological mediation — becomes an object of interface.

²⁰ From the Greek, “the one who brings solace”. Usually attributed to the Holy Ghost.

education *can* happen despite limited resources (Chen: 1996)²¹. It is not technology that is going to produce either good students or good teachers. First because learning is a complex system of human relations and implications, second because good students or good teachers cannot *be produced*. Trying to by-pass such living, creative system of relations, and even the role of teachers by technology, reveals a total lack of understanding and sensitivity about education.

2.4. EXAMINING THE DISCOURSE OF DEVELOPMENT

²¹ See: Chen, X. (1996): *Quality Schooling With Limited Resources, An international Comparison of Mathematics and Science Education in China, Korea and Hungary*, IIE; Stockholm University.

Besides, saying that learning is *dependent* upon economical and social conditions is the same as saying that intelligence; compassion or sensitivity is result of these conditions. Unfortunately the fact is that violence and ignorance has continued to prosper despite the conditions laid for the opposite to occur. This means that within the present education given in our societies, something continues amiss. If the favourable conditions allowed *real learning*, the learning that is acting intelligence, sensitivity, then affluent societies would have learned something more than what they did until now. And that would have been noticeable by now. This point should also be seen from other angle: it is obvious that without social and economic conditions, learning will be seriously jeopardised. Like, for example, the care that a mother gives to a child will be under harder test if the mother is living in miserable social and economic conditions. But it *does not* follow that good economical and social conditions will *necessarily* mean that the mother will be a good one. In the same way learning, which is a process of intelligence, needs a safe soil in order to be nurtured — not being, however, this learning a *result* of the given conditions; just like a mother's love is not the result of socio-economic conditions. Intelligence, sensitivity and compassion, lived by the individuals of a society, can bring about the favourable conditions for learning. These qualities can also develop the structural conditions that permit this learning process to bloom. These conditions obviously include basic material needs. However, these basic conditions, only by themselves, *per se*, will not bring about a new and evolved culture and society. In this sense, one can say, that education, learning, is an art. If it were an exclusively scientific process, — out of so much trial and error — by now the right formula would have already been discovered. The approach to come upon what this art might be is only possible through negation: One can only say what destroys that process, not what brings it about. Learning, like art, is not *dependent*, is not the *outcome* of any planned, engineered procedure. It is the expression of something impossible to grasp, not subject to be pinned down on a laboratory table for analysis. It is a creative event, a potential that unfolds. By this we can, now, clarify the term *potential* (Mautner: 2000: 440) by distinguishing it from *conditions of growth*: The conditions *are not* the potential. The potential does not unfold, come into being, due to the conditions. Conditions allow, permit and nourish something that, once again, one can repeat, is not itself product of manufacture. The creative element of learning, of art, is not the conditions — although these conditions allow the unfolding of art. The understanding that can be brought out of this is the following: good education is an inclusive process. It includes everything, makes use of everything that provides it nurture — this including material conditions, not being however a result of these. Like art makes use and has the need of tools like ink, paper, music instruments, etc. to express itself — but the spirit that animates art is not in these things. It is something — no matter how hard this might sound — indefinable.

At this point of the paper we will give attention to the discourse of progress that seems to be behind the great progressive and technological wave that is sweeping across the globe. For that, one question will be advanced:

Is development seen as:

1. a progressive becoming towards a goal, or
2. an unfolding process, with no goal?

We will start with the term "development" — development that usually comes *articulated* with a number of procedures that are forwarded in order to enact or achieve that same development.

The term development, as can be easily observed is, mostly, to be sensed in a progressive tense and form: there are those who are "developing", and those who have already *got there*, they are "developed". This implies a view of progression towards a goal, which goal when attained — past simple — is seen as a better state than the present continuous one. "Developed" is better than "developing". Development is seen as an arrow towards a better condition, which means that the ideal condition, the reality of the entity that is in a process of becoming, is either only attainable in the future — or has already been attained as a conclusive past. Development in this sense is a completely different thing from the one in which development is seen as an active present, non-impaired unfolding or flow, as a non-hindered event with no goal. (Bohm, 1980: xv)

In the previous paragraph, when it was referred that the term "development", when used in its first sense, usually comes articulated with a number of procedures, by these procedures one is meaning aid procedures. Out of a dysfunction of these procedures to attain their goal, which means *becoming developed*, another term comes onto the scene: reform.

Considering, again, the term "development" as associated with the classic image of a progressive, becoming seed turning into a flower, there are some considerations to

be taken. Seeing progress and becoming in both the case of a flower or a child or a country is very objectionable.

This development conception usually brings with it the sense of something becoming, fuller, brighter through time, in a teleological sense. From our point of view and experience, such a view is dangerously wrong. It is an Aristotelian and later on Hegelian view of an entity that, being substantially and essentially permanent, evolves through time (Russell: 2000: 179-80). Modern science²² and common sense show²³ us that there are no such monadic entities — immutably (in essence and substance) developing through different stages until finally (or not) becoming its own realised or manifested potential — but rather that there are inter-related events, each being like an unique active present flowering. Taking the example of the child for instance: the child is already, in the active present, its own total realised potential. This meaning that, at each moment the developing/unfolding individual is in its full bloom, and not that the future adult will become the finally realised potential of the present child.

The progressive/becoming conception is pervaded with both idealism and also a frustrated feeling of a continuously unachieved completion — which can be argued as misleading. The alternative view is that at each instant the individual is to be seen for what he **is**, and not for the becoming possibility, because that is non-existent. Seeing what the present situation is — and not what it might become or should be — is what in a present active brings about a change, when necessary.

On the other hand, what happens is that the progressive, becoming-something view often causes the present unfolding of individuals to be clouded by influence and moulding, regarding a future ideal. Progressive goals are set and from the moment the child or individual incorporates them, he will cease to be what he is — and will start living according to the ideal *image*, the goal image. The promise.

²² It is worthwhile to take into mind that in contemporary times Whitehead was one of the first contemporary scientists following the idea of reality as an universal movement, flux — such a reality being a form of a process, a torrent, in which not even its substance remains the same. Check, Whitehead (1993): *Process and Reality*, Macmillan, New York.

²³ In fact we *see*, and *sense* this never-ending movement. Right now moving clouds cross the sky, the sun is setting, one car passes producing a *doppler* effect, someone in other room moves — unbroken, the events flow into one another in an never-ceasing movement. Movement, in which, as the quantum theory puts it, the subject (the conscious entity) and the object (the contents of that consciousness) are mutually implicated *as one*. (Capra, 1982)

In our opinion children are, in fact, the biggest living example that contradicts the idea of progressive development. Quite the opposite, this progressive development is what in almost all the cases withers the flower of joy, curiosity and beauty from children's lives. It is a dangerous misconception that leads to the idea of the sophisticated adult being the truer condition, the blooming flower, the realised essence of the seed. Besides that, one will find here a mixed comparison between a material process — flowers and people *do* grow — and a consciousness (moral, spiritual, psychological, in its whole) process, in which it is considered that the entity is *becoming better*, which is, of course, debatable. However, this whole discussion can be taken from one another angle in which: the natural development is regarded as an unfolding movement of the whole, in which no moment or stage can be considered a higher, a more developed, or a truer point of the process.

2.5. MORE DEVELOPED, MORE EDUCATED... IS THAT BETTER? THE FALLACY OF THE PROGRESS DISCOURSE.

Let us start by objecting that so-called more educated societies are to be considered more developed, not even to say *better*. Regarding this point, we will give a very simple example: education as the means to a more civilised society is contradicted by the fact that, for example, tanks, machine-guns, chemical weapons, atom bombs and cloning were not invented, built and designed by illiterates. This might sound almost like a naive statement, but when observed more closely, leads to the conclusion that education, as we know it, is not addressing some of the main concerns and problems of human nature and reality. And, historically observing, education and so-called civilisation, with its high-culture peaks, cannot, definitely, be pointed out as the panacea for the human drama. It actually, and in many points, even contributed to it.

This paradox²⁴ shows that high-culture, education and esthetical love can go hand in hand with barbarism and cruelty. As Nietzsche wrote "almost everything that

²⁴ This statement can be understood in the gruesome paradox that Goebbels, for example, portrayed: Goebbels, being a lover of Goethe's poetry had his complete works in a volume with a cover made of Jew skin.

we call "higher culture" is based upon the spiritualising and intensifying of *cruelty*" (Russell: 2000: 733).

So, the point that is being made here is: no country, no culture has the moral legitimacy to consider itself an example or model, because culture and education are not in themselves — are not inherently — a good thing. They can be seen as an *expression of being* — expression that might, or might not, be well used. Nevertheless culture and education cannot be defended as an intrinsically good thing in itself. Therefore, promoting, insisting or imposing *a specific type of education* as the solution to the world's evils is not a very different attitude as that of the European missionaries that imposed the word of God upon the Africans or Brazilian Indians. The gospel, for the missionaries was, then, the symbol of education, civilisation and moral superiority. Nevertheless, societies, like the Western one, whose culture, whose education *did not* serve to prevent the horrors that the present century has witnessed, societies like this one do not have the legitimacy of presenting their educational system — which is a direct result of their culture — as the solution for world's problems. But the promoting, the proselytising proceeds and

In fact, if you look a bit further in history, you'll find that all this is completely familiar. It is a kind of tragic — or worse, maybe obscene — replay of what was going on a century ago. Just a century ago, there was the same talk about how the enlightened states must bring civilisation to the backward people of the world, and must disregard sovereignty or anything else, because they have the mission of bringing civilisation, Christianity, and human rights. (...) Well, we know exactly what the consequences of that were. We don't have to wait to see; we have a century of history to show how that enlightenment was brought to the world. Is there any reason for expecting this phase of it to be any different? Most of the world doesn't think so. Outside the self-defined enlightened states, there's plenty of fear and concern over the revival of some of the worst days of European imperialism and the arrogance and self-adulation that went along with it. (Chomsky, 1999: 13)

Institutions, organisations, governments are, in fact, to be understood as machines of great sophistication of violence (Hoppers: 1998)²⁵. So, in the present

²⁵ For a very interesting analysis of *Structural Violence* in the big institutions, organisations et al, check: HOPPERS, C. (1998): *Structural Violence as a Constraint to African Policy Formation in the 1990's*:

society, where these big organisations and institutions are becoming fuzzier and increasingly powerful, the threat is even bigger.

Moreover, at the level of the individual, if education, as we know it, was the element that made the human being better, then children would be the basest of them all, because they have not been yet educated. This runs against our empirical knowledge. On the other hand, if education is necessary in order control the growing vices and bad tendencies that human beings might have in their maturing process, then it is to be concluded that the natural development of this same human being is an evil that must be repressed, conditioned and diverted towards better goals.

Seeing, likewise, individual genius as a result of a conjectural historical progress is also incorrect. One can say, that apart from technological advancements, human intelligence has not evolved at all during its known history. What can be observed in history is "island-conflagrations" of order and intelligence, not a progression. These islands of intelligence and order are irruptive and timeless in the sense that they do not depend on a chain-progressive conception of time. Most countries nowadays are in more disorder than the kingdom of Asoka (264-228 BC), and one cannot argue that men like Heraclitus (500? BC), Shakyamuni Buddha (563? - 483? BC), Dogen Zenji (1200? AD) or Shakespeare (1564 – 1616) were less gifted than any forefront contemporary intellectual. In such cases an unfolding process was allowed to happen, intelligence and order flourished despite a technological and progressive time conception.

With the failing of *progressing* sensed by the institutions and governments, reforms come into light. But the concept of reform is also, itself, attached to a Darwinian and Aristotelian ingrained belief in a substance that progresses, something permanent that simply changes form, hopefully to the better. However, it can be pointed out that there is neither such linear progress, nor a substance that "progresses". In contemporary science, evolution is no more seen as a matter of the survival of the fittest

Repositioning Education in International Relations, Institute of International Education, Stockholm University, Stockholm. For *structural violence* can be understood "when force is not exerted wilfully by a person but by a structure created and perpetuated by a custom or law (...) when human beings are being influenced so that their actual somatic and mental realisations are below their potential realisations". (Hoppers: 1988: 43)

in a desperate race where, one by one, the weaker are dropped off, but it is rather a matter of continual adaptation, *assimilation*, transformation, mutation. In this sense, the human ability to survive will depend not on conquering but *understanding* — it is a matter of intelligent insights. Scientific discoveries and art creations happen in such an unpredictable way: through a sudden glimpse into the ever-changing workings of nature (Kuhn, 1970: 111). True scientific revolutions are the absolute going-beyond, *not the reform*, of a paradigm. They are the perception of an absolutely new theory and paradigm. They are the perception of a new order (Capra: 1982: xxviii), present *between the lines*.

These glimpses can be considered as mental mutations and inner revolutions — they are the unpredictable and intelligent element of change and mutation (Gleick, 1998:35). This is what can bring about evolution and revolution from within, individually and, also consequently, catalytically for the whole of society.

To make the point of this chapter: clear we defend that culture and education, as they are presently understood and practised in our society, do not uproot the mechanisms of cruelty and egotism from the human being. In the researcher's opinion, *these* — violence and egotism — are, in fact, the main reasons why development is suffocated and learning does not flourish amongst most humans. Actually, education, culture and organised institutions, as they are known, even help this violence and egotism to become more sophisticated and damaging.

We now realise that extremes of collective hysteria and savagery can coexist with parallel conservation and, indeed, further development of the institutions, bureaucracies and professional codes of high culture. In other words, the libraries, museums, theatres, universities, research centres, in and through which the transmission of the humanities and of the sciences mainly takes place, can prosper next to concentration camps (...) We know also — and here is knowledge thoroughly documented but in no way, as yet, incorporated in a rational psychology — that obvious qualities of literate response, aesthetic feeling, can coexist with barbaric, politically sadistic behaviour in the same individual. Men such as Hans Frank who administered the "final solution" in eastern Europe were avid connoisseurs and, in some instances, performers of Bach and Mozart. We know of personnel in the bureaucracy of the tortures and of the ovens who cultivated a knowledge of Goethe, a love of Rilke. The facile evasion "such men did not understand the poems they read or the music they knew and seemed to play so well" will not do.

There simply is no evidence that they were more obtuse than anyone else to the human genius, to the enacted moral energies of great literature and of art. One of the principal works that we have in the philosophy of the language, in the total reading of Holderlin's poetry, was composed almost within earshot of a death camp. Heidegger's pen did not stop nor his mind go mute (...) Our present knowledge of a negative transfer from civilisation to behaviour, in the individual and the society, runs counter to the faith, to the operative assumptions, on which the progress of education, of general literacy, of scholarship and the dissemination of the arts were grounded. (Steiner, 1971: 63-64)

In this sense, one can repeat, apart from the technological aspect, there has been no progress, no evolution, only a change of vocabulary. What the human being has to learn in order to become complete as an individual (a non-fragmentary, indivisible whole, non-dependent on external help to be engineered even inwardly), is that mutational quality, that inner revolution that, like compassion and empathy, cannot be taught, just learned (Krishnamurti; 1981: 11). There are no aid agencies, no institutions or schools that can awaken that in humans.

From this follows thus the mutual responsibility of:

1. The human community in laying the peaceful and secure foundations that guarantees the safety and freedom of its successive generations to adventure into the territory where there is no authority. Therefore, these societies would need to be small, self-reliant, and not dependent on imported and transplanted formulas or systems. These societies would have to discover the means for their unfolding from their own context, from their own soil, not being passively subject to the authority of the "best", or of the "best practices" (Samoff: 2001). Moreover, in such small, self-sufficient societies, the impact of an individual is much greater — consequently the individual would feel his enormous responsibility towards the whole. Conversely, these societies would provide a coherent basis and context for the unfolding of the individual, like good soil nurtures a seed, allowing it to express itself. These societies would represent human-scale societies.

2. The individual, in his turn, would have to waken in himself the responsibility to be self-motivated in his search, discovery and learning process, without expecting to

be lead and taught — without needing to continuously rely on authority. Such an individual process of unfolding would, naturally, represent development for the whole. Even though society should provide nurture, the seed itself has to be strong and interested — the individual has to be his own guiding lighthouse. It is obvious that in order to bring about a sane and free society, firstly, an inner revolution at individual level is necessary. This *turning point*, this *metanoia*²⁶ is the individual unfolding necessary for a new type of culture to bloom and flourish. Because, as Lao Tzu states in the *Tao Te Ching*: “Wanting to reform the world without discovering one’s true self is like trying to cover the world with leather to avoid the pain of walking on stones and thorns. It is much simpler to wear shoes”.

So when it is said that it cannot be taught, just learned, it is clear that any state sponsored institution, any government, big organisation or big machine alike is an even more helpless entity to do this: to teach, or even lay the foundations of *that* which is so important to learn. That which is the seed of an unfolding potentiality cannot be taught or given from outside, much less by institutions or organisations. Nevertheless, the latter are substituting, in very destructive ways, the human-scale societies, to the individual, and to the natural ways of relation and learning. They are engineering the social and individual — with disastrous consequences for both. As Fuller writes, *it is institutions that define how children grow up* (p. 25), and:

Western advocates of *modernisation* make two central arguments. First, secular nation-wide institutions must be constructed to replace local collectivities and ethnic affiliations, manifest in village, church, and family units. (...) Second, the individual, when detached from traditional and local authority and fused to the secular state, will be motivated to serve national commitments. Mass schooling is the instrument that socialises children toward central authority and modern affiliations. (Fuller, 1991: 26)

If the outside influence (aid) of the affluent countries were be understood, exclusively, as a means to secure basic material needs necessary to life (food, clothes,

²⁶ From the Greek “radical change of heart”.

shelter, medicine) to be provided to needing countries, it would be understandable. But it is not. In fact most of it is just progress-discourse, just promise. It is dangerous idealism.

Affluent countries, through institutions — when deciding upon *how* to live life and *what* to learn elsewhere — are applying, in our opinion, the "gentle-jingoism" equation.

2.6. A GENTLE JINGOISM

The comparison-equation of "gentle-jingoism" that is applied, by the affluent countries in their conception of aid and help, is the following:

Y considers himself better (e.g. more developed, more educated, etc.) than **X**.

Y, being gentle and having good intentions, decides to help **X**. **Y** decides to help **X** by helping **X** to become like **Y**.

Two immediate questions can be put:

Is **Y**, in fact, more developed and educated than **X**? According to which scale of development and education? Can it not be argued that much of that measuring is done, by **Y**, according to a scale of power and wealth - and not a few times boosted at the expenses of **X**?

How can anyone, in this case **Y**, know what is best for another? Moreover, how to know what is best for entire nations and continents? (Much of the "helping" ends up being like "forcibly helping the old lady to cross the road", as the Portuguese saying goes. *Maybe* that is not what she needs.).

This (un)conscious attitude is the following:

1. Y considers himself developed and good

2. desires to help and, consequentially, to make others according to his own image.

A commentary should now be added. In the Genesis there is a description of the ideal earth, description in which one can even see the lion eating grass together with the lamb. Well, this is the notion of a earthly paradise according to *one very particular type* of mental frame and view of the reality. We bring up this point for the following reason: although the policy makers, and the policy reports assure that local, indigenous and specific cultures will be integrated and preserved — this is doubtful. The great-scale interference (which is not the same as *participation*) in these cultures is of great impact. This is an historical fact older even than the arrival of the Europeans to the Americas. This interference is a direct result of an old dream: the conception of "one Catholic religion, one universal culture, and one world-wide State, [a thing which] has haunted men's thoughts ever since its approximate realisation by Rome" (Russell; 2000: 287). And, although nowadays the discourse has softened its edges, and there is the given guarantee that the particular, local idiosyncrasies will be preserved and admitted intact into the affluent-country club, this is the same as when the lion is admitted into the Genesis paradise: it will be put eating grass together with the lamb. To be able to fit into that *particular and specific* concept of harmony and order, the *natural order*, the nature of the lion will have to have been adapted, engineered. According to the concept of "paradise" of the affluent countries, certain realities will have to be, definitely, adapted, tamed and clothed into new and more suitable roles.

However, it has been seen that it is not so easy to help **X** to become like **Y**. As Samoff puts it:

It seems that the currently dominant global development strategies will expand rather than reduce the gaps between the most and least affluent, both across and within countries, leaving the Third World farther and farther behind. (Samoff, 2001: .12)

Failing in the process of helping, a whole policy of reform is enacted.

To (re)form will, then, mean, as pointed out before, to mould and re-mould, into new shapes, the same original tendency. The tendency is a gentle jingoism, itself an euphemistic reform of the old colonial machine.

2.7. WHAT KIND OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ARE WE TALKING ABOUT?

It should now be interesting to give some attention to the following point:

What is meant by "education" when it is being planned, reformed, proselytised, promoted, analysed? Is it

1. skills learning and skills teaching? or
2. something as vague as values, free-thought, aesthetics and ethics, something that sounds nearly mystic, religious? or
3. both, a cocktail of the two previous points?

What is being conceptualised when the term education is used? Drills, tests, skills and their technical competence and performance? Or a "something" that awakens a deep understanding of life, nurtures ethics and values, something that instils democracy, tolerance, love to learn, learning to learn, self-discovery, respect, artistic taste, etc.?

If it is the former of the concepts that is being applied when talking about education, why is there, then, such great trouble in evaluating, adapting, increasing and optimising its sophistication? Education, in this sense is like a machine — it is a rather mechanical, technological and progressive object that can easily evolve according to the previous knowledge. (The methods of teaching languages, for example, have seen various phases, and accordingly, after trial and testing, several positive conclusions can be attained that enable subjects to become proficient in lesser time and teaching become more effective).

If it is the option 2, then education, on a massive scale is trying to substitute itself to family, religion, art — becoming either

a) vague (the values instituted are not clear, are fuzzy and represent an amalgam of many fragmentary interests) and hegemonic (however many interests are involved, the final version presented in school becomes the canon), or

b) ideal, utopian (trying through the means of the classroom to put young people on a path of self-discovery and search of knowledge) and thus self-contradictory, because it evaluates, enforces, compels (compulsory attendance), directs (through curricula) and sorts (because not all the students will, in the end, be seen as equal).

If it is an attempt of simultaneously doing both the option 1 and 2, it is not surprising that no-one is really satisfied with the result. The expectations that are felt in relation to this enormous final solution are necessarily frustrated and cut short. The enterprise is too vast and self-contradictory, it promises individual freedom, but results in massification and conditioning through grading, sorting. The expectations for what institutional education can and *should* do are so big that satisfaction is never attained, either by one particular group of interests, or for them all, with the latter case being the most common one, in which all blame one another for the leaks, contradictions and failures (we are thinking of the case of Portugal, where teachers from the Right blame the ones from the Left, and all of them blame the socialists, and *vice-versa*, etc.)²⁷

With such a scenario, the avalanche of continuous, on-going, almost overlapping reforms, protests, adjustments and re-adjustments is not surprising. Together with this more technical side of the process, goes a strong feeling of frustration that, at moments, amounts to plain impotence or a notion of absurd and futility in it all. *The machine is not responding accordingly*. Most of the educational policies and reforms end up being like, as the Zen saying goes, "trying to catch a feather with a fan". The intention, nobody doubts it, is good. But the result seems to fall short of the intention. As Schwab²⁸ wrote in *Newsweek* (July 30):

²⁷ We are also recalling the case of an educational policy maker from SIDA who bitterly criticised the stubbornness and resistance of Bolivian teachers in accepting the reforms proposed by SIDA. Nobody thought of asking "why should they"? (During the course given by Joel Samoff at SIDA, April 2001)

As we survey the challenges of the new century, it is hard to escape a dismaying conclusion. The global institutions that we have so painstakingly built over the past half century — the United Nations, the IMF and World Bank — are inadequate to deal with the many problems we face. This fact of “systematic failure” threatens us all. It prompts the United States and other powerful nations to act unilaterally when their interests are threatened. That, in turn, can easily degenerate into national and regional protectionism. It has also sparked a powerful (and increasingly violent) backlash against globalisation by those who feel frustrated or overwhelmed by the sheer complexity and pace of change. I am deeply skeptical, at this point, that the institutions responsible for promoting world peace, financial stability, socioeconomic development and the free flow of goods and services will ever again be able to address these challenges on their own (...) Growing interdependence means that we must move toward accepting the reality of a truly globalised society — encompassing and drawing strength from our political differences and our cultural diversity and commanding reflection and collaboration among leaders from all sectors of global society, not just governments.” (Schwab: 2001: 16)

2.8. BIG MECHANIC STRUCTURES AS SOURCES OF SENILITY.

One type of education world-wide. Who decides?

In order to bring about the educational structure envisaged by the "world agenda", an enormous articulate system — an enormous machine will have to be distributed. As shown before, this double bladed system — which includes skills and values — will represent *one* type of perception of reality, one inclination to certain skills and certain values. This, obviously, implies a growing homogeneity, as seen by the educational curriculum spreading around the globe. Even the fact that such a word as *curriculum* (meaning in Latin "narrow path") is being used, should give rise to questions. (Also interestingly enough, in languages from Latin origin, the word *curro* means the path along which bulls are lead into the arena during bullfight). Regarding education, what is observable is that a linear, taxonomic system by stages, a certain standardised concept of learning is being implemented and spread all over, the so-called

²⁸ Schwab is founder and chairman of the World Economic Forum.

world curriculum (Meyer: 2000)²⁹. Asian children will have to learn English and how to use computers in order to be someone in life, but English, Portuguese or Swedish children will never practice *shikantaza zazen*³⁰ nor will they, most probably, ever know what it is. Nevertheless, *it could* be argued that the latter is *as* or more important for the human learning than the former.

In order to apply the "one global educational system" (even considering that it might have its local variants), a system that ought to be seen as a complex or non-linear system (thus subject to the laws of non-linear systems)³¹ is being directed towards its subjects. A form of structured and organised power is being directed, namely, towards the students, children and the nations in general where this mechanic system is being introduced. And the question is not even if it is "*this*" system, but that *a* highly mechanistic system of organised Education is being introduced everywhere.

So, presently, what we want to examine and point at, is the connection between some highly structured and organised power, and processes of senility and corruption. In our opinion, we consider that there are clear signs of senility manifest in highly sophisticated structures and systems, which do not obey fluid, organic and creative laws — but quite the opposite, tend to continuously bring about mechanistic responses. By this is meant that we will imply *a relation between highly mechanistic systems and structures that represent the iron law of oligarchy*³², and processes of senility and corruption.

²⁹ Seminar by J. Meyer on "Globalisation and the Curricula" held in SU (03/02/00)

³⁰ This is known as the practice of doing-nothing, or just sitting, or letting things flow. It could also be said to be the non-practice of deep observation. For a very interesting discussion about this remarkable and subtle art of spontaneous understanding, and learning, see: Dogen Zenji, Zazengi, in *Shobogenzo*, Book 3, Windbell Publications, Tokyo & London

³¹ A straightforward example of the mutual relation principles that rule non-linear systems (including, obviously, mechanical ones): let us suppose that one wants to calculate the speed of a hockey puck on an ice field. "Without friction a simple linear equation expresses the amount of energy you needed to accelerate the hockey puck. With friction the relationship gets complicated, because the amount of energy changes depending on how fast the puck is already moving. Nonlinearity means that the act of playing the game has a way of changing the rules. You cannot assign a constant importance to friction, because its importance depends on speed. Speed, in turn, depends on friction. That twisted changeability makes nonlinearity hard to calculate, but it also creates rich kinds of behaviour that never occur in linear systems". (Gleick: 1998: 24)

³² This is an extremely important concept, which pervades our dissertation and has had a "profound effect on thinking about larger systems, especially the modern state" (Johnson: 2000: 213). *The iron law of oligarchy* is a term coined by Robert Michels (1967) in his *Political Parties*, Free Press, New York. According to the *Collins Dictionary of Sociology*, the iron law of oligarchy is the tendency of "political organisations, trade unions to become oligarchic, however much they may seek internal democracy."

In this sense, in order to organise a complex mechanistic system like the pan-educational one, and disseminate it throughout the world, its organic-like procedure will have to obey massive, iron laws similar to those of the implementation of the *State or Cities*³³. We will use this highly allegoric comparison for the reason that both State and Cities represent highly articulate and sophisticated systems of subjection, conditioning and exploitation, being the “secondary products of authority” (Kaldhun: 1980: 235). As it is described in the Muqaddimah, these "vast constructions"

are not among the things that are necessary matters of great concern to human beings, in the sense that all human beings desire them or feel compelled to have them. As a matter of fact, (human beings) must be forced or driven to (build cities). The stick of royal authority is what compels them, or they may be stimulated by promise of reward and compensation. (Khalidun: 1980: 235)

Both the State and City are places of concentrated power — in a military, monetary and decision-making sense. And that power is to be understood as having a source, a centre and root, located *not* in the individuals situated within the events of a context, but in the alien and “multiple network of diverse elements — walls, space allocation, institutions, rules, discourse” that try to control the outcome of these events

Once these structures move “beyond the fluid participatory structures which often accompany their formation, they inevitably become more bureaucratic and more centrally controlled, falling under the domination of a professional leadership. In this process, the original goals of the organisation may also be replaced by more narrowly instrumental goals including a concern for the maintenance of the organisation”. There are three sets of factors that are identified in this process, namely 1) technical factors, meaning the “need to maintain an effective **fighting machine**, but when this happens the machine develops its own vested interests, and is able to control agenda and communications, manage internal opposition”, etc.; 2) Psychological characteristics of mass, i.e., that the rank and file members of these big organised structures “tend to be apathetic, are willing to be led, are readily swayed by mass oratory, and venerate leadership”; and 3) such leadership being characterised by a tendency to “cling to power at all costs”. (Jary&Jary: 1995:339).

Due to the importance of this concept we decided to cross its definition with the one given by *The Blackwell Dictionary of Sociology*, according to which the *iron law of oligarchy* is “inevitable in large, complex societies”. And such systems become oligarchic because 1) “people generally prefer to let others make decisions for them; 2) the system’s complexity makes it impossible for people to know enough to participate intelligently in decision-making, and, as a result, makes leaders increasingly indispensable; and 3) those who achieve Authority are unwilling to give up the resulting privileges and Prestige, and thus try to consolidate and extend their power in order to keep them. As a result the leader’s goal and power are increasingly concentrated”.(Johnson: 2000: 213)

³³ “Human cultures were originally **homeostatic**; they existed in a self-sustained equilibrium, with no notions of time and progress, like we have got. Then the city-virus got in. (...) like all viral organisms, its

(Foucault: 1977: 307). People are, then, alienated from their own force³⁴. This can be illustrated with the following example:

1) event **X** is, for example, the dynamic energy generated by individual work, 2) the alien power is to be seen as the capacity of utilising the energy of this event **X** towards specific goals, i.e., this work is being transformed, for example, in taxes that are applied in decisions that often go against the will of the informed individual. (Decisions related to issues such as, say, environment, armament, animal experimentation, food industry, certain television programs, etc). So the power is not located in the individual and his actual work, but in the alien channels that divert and apply the energy, *resulting from that work*, elsewhere, outside the event that generated such energy — in this case the individual work. States and Cities are constructed with such a principle: the energy produced is mainly diverted towards a few interests and goals. Interests and goals that only represent a few perceptions and conceptions of reality. Goals and interests that are promoted as being of general interest by the means of propaganda, conditioning, education. Goals and interests mainly connected with consumerism and conditioning. Conditioning towards consumerism of certain goals and interests, like the case of a specific organised education as pointed out in previous chapters.

Again we remind the reader that the point of this chapter is to relate these structured, mechanic powers, like States, Cities and pandemic educational systems to an intrinsic tendency towards senility and corruption. This, not to say a degradation of the moral values, natural bonds and human bravery — leading to a progressive dependence of people upon others (Khaldun: 1980: 267). The basic premise defended by us is that the necessarily mechanical processes of power involved in the generation

one directive is to use all available resources in producing **copies** of itself. More and more copies until there is no raw material left and the host body, overwhelmed, can only die.” (Morrison: 1996: 83).

³⁴ For more detailed discussion on the term *alienation* see note 75. Regarding the present paragraph, and following the same line of the *Oxford Dictionary of Sociology*, what we are pointing at is the fact that people’s control over their own work, and the energy which from that results, escapes their reach — and is, thus, alienated (Marshall: 1998: 13-14).

of these big systems bring about various corruptive effects both at a macro-level in the system itself, and at a micro-level in the individual's brain³⁵.

This should be understood. It shows that the goal of civilisation is sedentary culture and luxury. When civilisation reaches that goal, it turns towards corruption and starts being senile (...). Indeed, we may say that the qualities of character resulting from sedentary culture and luxury are identical with corruption. Man is a man only in as much as he is able to procure for himself useful things and to repel harmful things, and in as much as his character is suited to making efforts to this effect. The sedentary person cannot take care of his needs personally. He may be too weak, because of the tranquillity he enjoys. Or he may be too proud, because he was brought up in prosperity and luxury. Both things are blameworthy. He also is not able to repel harmful things, because he has no courage as the result of (his life in) luxury and his upbringing under the (tyrannical) effect of education and instruction. He thus becomes dependent upon a protective force to defend him. (Khalidun: 1980: 296-7)

"Sedentary culture is the goal of civilisation. It means the end of its life span and brings about it corruption" (Khalidun: 1980: 291)³⁶. Any form of highly organised mechanism tends to bring about *repetition and routine*, which can be pointed out as a source of physical corruption even at the brain level³⁷. The only way of keeping such big machines (world-states, megalopolis and a world-wide educational system) going as the ones idealised, namely, by contemporary affluent societies, is by the means of highly sophisticated structures of habit and routine. No matter how creative the system might pretend to be: The fact is that, springing from a particular source, from a centre of

³⁵ For one approach to this subject read the discussion between Bohm, Krishnamurti and G. Narayan (Principal of the Rishi Valley School in India), Chapter 9 of *The Ending of Time* (1985), Harper Collins, New York.

³⁶ Khalidun in *The Muqaddimah* refers to the desert people as examples of people that, in a more instinctive and intuitive way are able to keep a simple and moral life. The simplicity and morality of the so-called backward people is also thoroughly documented in articles by Helena Norberg-Hodge, *Learning From the Ladakh*; and Marshall Sahlins, *The Original Affluent Society*, in Rahnama, M.; Bawtree, V. (2001): *The Post-Development Reader*, David Philip, Cape Town; Fernwood Publishin, Halifax, Nova Scotia; Zed Books, London&New Jersey pp. 3-29. We would also like to call attention to the researches done by Théodore Monod about the desert and nomadic people, that are being killed through a "spiritual strangling" (Monod: 1998: 64). As he puts it: "In order to solve the problem related with the so-called underdeveloped nomads, the Governments want to make them sedentary. Put in other words: they want their mental death. Freedom is a thing that is not loved. Made sedentary, the nomads are neutralised, suffocated. (...) Men has abandoned what is cosmic, the fascination for the universal, for the totality" thus becoming "an Homo *urbicus*, without relation with the cosmos that is part of his own flesh. The city has made man sedentary." (Monod: 1989: 64,7. Our translation)

³⁷ On research regarding brain shrinkage see note 40

power, this system has to obey mechanic patterns of function. And these patterns are necessarily concentric and limited because they are the result of human mental constructions, *specific* theories that might be, or have been, adequate in one particular instant and context — but, *not* in all instants and contexts.

Big structures born out of human thought are, to start with, self-contradictory due to the mostly dualistic nature of thought itself³⁸. Furthermore, human thought is doomed to profound limitation at all levels inclusively in its capacity of abstraction, which means that creating an abstract and ideal structure to be applied everywhere means denying the *infinite span of implications* that reality lays beyond the possibilities of human thought. The fact “is that the world which we want to explore is a largely unknown entity” (Fayerabend: 1975: 20).

The brain by such procedures is, possibly, trying to attain absolute security from the continuous challenge posed by reality. It is also trying to secure a field of authority and certainties. However, no matter how understandable this process might be, the result is physically and psychologically corruptive and narrowing — as seen in the senility found both in the contemporary society and the brain (Capra, 1982).

As one of the outcomes of this process of search for security and authority, one myth then takes form: The myth associated with mechanistic scientism and the consequent belief, once again, in progress — in how things *should* be. But the myth is

of no objective relevance; it continues to exist solely as the result of the effort of the community of believers and of their leaders, be these now priests or Noble prize winners. This, I think, is the most decisive argument against any method that encourages uniformity, be it empirical or not. It enforces an unenlightened conformism, and speaks of truth; it leads to a deterioration of

³⁸ Thought is in continuous conflict due to the dualistic process between *what is* and *what should be*. Let us consider the following example: one person considers children essentially good. When facing horrible deeds and crimes, committed by children, this person will refer back to his system of beliefs, explanations and justifications, to what children should be, instead of just facing what is present before the eyes, i.e. the cruelty, and violence of children. *What is* is that, in some contexts, some children *are* cruel, violent etc. but not excluding other things too. Nevertheless there is the homogenising tendency, be it in science, religion, etc. of getting attached to one conception, one perception, one abstraction, and to apply it indiscriminately. And, naturally, everything that is not like it *should be* brings about conflict and inner contradiction. Actually this can be seen in most aspects of our society: laws are drawn, rules are accepted, systems are believed — and continuously broken, by-passed. People consider that they should be tolerant, peaceful, respectful, etc. But what is going on *in* themselves is completely different, and facing this contradiction in oneself — by comparing the distance between one’s actions (what is) and one’s ideal image (what should be) — further conflict arises. This is what we mean by thought dualism.

intellectual capabilities, of the power of imagination, and speaks of deep insight; it destroys the most precious gift of the young — their tremendous power of imagination, and speaks of education. (Feyerabend: 1975: 45)

It is believed that if scientific procedures are applied in relation to the constructions of thought (forgetting that they are, themselves, a product of thought), reliable results might be produced. For this reason, even in social sciences, there is the tendency to try to make the whole business as scientific as possible, as if by means of the discovery and encompassing of the multiple variables in presence and their implications, a reliable system, an all-unifying epistemological prescription could appear to light. However, even

Schizophrenics very often hold beliefs which are as rigid, all pervasive, and unconnected with reality, as are the best dogmatic philosophies. However, such beliefs come to them naturally whereas a 'critical' philosopher may sometimes spend his whole life attempting to find arguments which create a similar state of mind. (Feyerabend: 1975: 45)

The problem then is that, this method is itself the product of a very limited thought set and even if there is chance of uncovering some scientific laws underlying the social reality, these laws will necessarily have to belong to a world where there is relativity, quantum indeterminacy, and chaos. And if social sciences are presently facing a crisis, it is “essentially a crisis of perception”, that

derives from the fact that we are trying to apply the concepts of an outdated world view — mechanistic world view of Cartesian-Newtonian science — to a reality that can no longer be understood in terms of these concepts. We live today in a globally interconnected world, in which biological, psychological, social, and environmental phenomena are all interdependent. To describe this world appropriately we need an ecological perspective which the Cartesian world does not offer.” (Capra: 1982: xviii).

So, however *scientific* the social-sciences might try to be, the reality is that, presently, they are a system of beliefs (and, unfortunately, of dogmas) as scientific as voodoo (Feyerabend: 1975: 48). Social sciences, which do not themselves have a sharp perception and insight into deeper orders and relations are, definitely, not representing

reality appropriately. This because all-mighty science itself is a limited, myth-like interpretation of reality and as fallible as anything else — because it is product of that, *per se*, very barren process³⁹, known as *thought*. And as a consequence of taking its mechanistic representation, theory, too seriously Science has nowadays become the "most recent, most aggressive, and most dogmatic religious institution" (Feyerabend: 1975: 295).

What is being meant is the following: any designed system whatsoever represents a structure of power, isomorphism and violence, not only at the social level but at the psychological/brain level as well. Any *engineered* system whatsoever is not a (be it called *scientific or natural*) *truth* proved to be universally the best. Besides, most theories, representations, and structures soon lose their initial fluidity and, as we have been pointing out, tend towards the iron law of oligarchy.

The only way to make people fit into a mechanistic system (be it a State, a City or an organised system of learning) is by some form of enforcement or proselytising. The brain has to be *physically affected* in its synapse cross connections in order to follow specific functioning ruts, specific tracks of thought and perception. Within highly organised structures — such as cities, states and educational systems — the brain has to act within and follow very specific tracks, preferring certain lines and synapse cross connections that end up being over-abused and too often repeated, and consequently becoming too fixed (Krishnamurti&Bhom: 1985: 186).

The whole life style lived in our present society illustrates this. The scheduled days and years, the timetables, the standardisation of experiences, the office life, the resigned queues, the 9 to 5 jobs for 45 years, the schools and classrooms — everything is extremely mechanised, predictable and sedentary⁴⁰. This routine and habit leads to a

³⁹ Barren and rigid as it can be when it has imprisoned itself in one frozen and static frame— when it is not touched by a disposition to learn; when it is not open to be touched by insight and new perceptions. For a discussion on the connection between material processes (of matter) in general and the functioning of thought and the difference between mechanistic thought processes and intelligence see Bohm: 1980: 217.

⁴⁰ For a very interesting research done by Bristol's University about this question of *time-zone allocation and its connection with temporal lobe atrophy and spatial cognitive deficits*, see Kwangwook Cho's article, in *Nature Neuroscience*, 4, (June 2001), pp. 567-568. The research points at the fact that spatial-temporal structures experienced by the brain *do have* a direct physical impact upon the brain matter itself — following that, long term repetition of certain spatial-temporal structures *do cause* a physical shrinkage of the brain.

great need of entertainment and escapism in order to relieve the boredom, stress – in order to break down the narrow circularity of tension and automatisations felt down to the body itself. And the tendency is for this concept of existence to become world-wide. As Bohm puts it: "It seems that before man was organised into society, he was living close to nature, and it was not possible to live in routine" (Krishnamurti&Bohm: 1985: 181) — therefore no corruption to the extent we nowadays see it in the so-called civilised societies.

Still regarding the question of making such a system more *scientific* (in order to predict, plan or control it), such a wish is utopian because the variables and implications are infinite. There is no civilisation (Toynebee: 1972: chaps. 4,5), city, formula, scientific theory that, *due to its own intrinsic impermanent nature*, is not on its way to dissolution. So, trying to perpetuate such types of systems is a mirage. Besides that, even if those scientific laws could be found, they would, again, belong to an area of science in which science verges on what, nowadays, is still seen as almost unscientific. This is in case of contemporary science: events (social, psychological, material, environmental, etc, etc.) have to be observed under a light of unpredictability, multidimensionality, non-linear interrelatedness and wholeness.

Human thought, and the resulting structures born from a will to create a massive, fixed, engine-like, self-supporting mechanistic system end up as thought and structures of

1) conflict, because they are self-contradictory, 2) violence, because they are defensive and deny the unpredictable unfolding of reality, 3) power assertive and enforcing, because they try to fix reality to the initial set of propositions and abstractions which idealised that same reality and consequently 4) become corrupt and senile because they tend to act within a limited field of mechanical possibilities, developing in patterns of self-interest, within routines and repetitive habits that guarantee security and patterned self-expansion. This is seen even at the cellular level of the brain, causing it to be materially damaged and worn out, because "our perception is generally directed by knowledge, *by the past*, which is knowledge perceiving, and with action arising, acting

from *that* [past]. This is a factor of shrinking of the brain, of senility.” (Krishnamurti&Bhom: 1985: 189)

Now, even if such a big structure as a world-wide educational system could be enforced, such a system would also, necessarily, contain in itself the seed of chaos. Any non-linear or complex system is fated to that. As Samoff (2001)⁴ pointed out, the educational system can be compared to two aeroplanes that take off side by side. It is enough that the slightest deviation occurs — and it always does — that the parallel flight is doomed to last little. So, paradoxically if the machines keep *a fixed* route, not allowing for continuous adaptation, the route will end up being completely altered and, most specially, the destination will be completely different from the one initially planned due to its sensitive dependence on initial conditions.

Policy making in education is usually, then, like trying to predict the outcome of a big complex system whilst ignoring that the slightest deviation enacts unexpected consequences, and that “every process is partially of totally interfered by chance, so much that under natural circumstances a course of events absolutely conforming to specific laws is almost an exception” (Jung: 1989: xxii). If this was understood, how could different cases then be compared? How could statistics be so used and trusted? How could planning ahead be based on the experiences of other countries?

As is clearly shown by the chaos theory and quantum mechanics, statistics, reforms and planning ahead are as fallible as the forecasts and predictions of ancient "bowel readers". They are as reliable as the predictions of the oracle that interpreted the will of the god or the symbols gathered from synergetic events. Trying to understand the present Leviathanic educational system is like interpreting the oracle⁴¹ — and doing education policy is like casting the Tarot cards. In most cases, statistics end up being as useful to solve today's Educational problems as last week's lottery numbers are useful for one to succeed in next week's winning combination.

⁴ Course given by Samoff at Sida, April 2001

⁴¹ With this we do not mean that predictions are absurd. We mean that what one is going to see and read is probably, like in the case of the oracle, the projection, the echo, of the contents of his own mind and knowledge. (For an interesting discussion on this topic see Foreword by C. G. Jung to the *I Ching or Book of Changes*, Penguin, London, pp. xxxviii-xxxix).

Summarising, we can say that the point we are concerned with here is the following: With the will to bring about the specific conditions that are considered necessary to certain a concept of development and education, there are specific formulas that are applied. However, these formulas are the result of the environment that brought them into being. The means and actions that can bring about development and grounds for learning might, and actually are never the same, in two places, two cultures. Such a conception is what we consider one of the biggest misunderstandings. The possibility to bring about any sort of development and learning has to be the fruit of an environment of holistic learning. Learning has its roots in its own soil, is creation at an individual level — in deep connection with its context and its challenges. This means that this development, this education cannot be a transplanted machine, a transplanted world-view, but it is the result of a deep understanding and action facing its own present situations⁴². To bring about the environment for a serious development and learning, there are no best practices, *but* the ones created by those involved in the situation to be solved. Any kind of formula (no matter how scientific it might pretend to be), any kind of *the* “best practice” is a temptation towards imposition of mechanisms and blue-prints — which end up being an iron law of oligarchy.

3. THE *PROGRESSING* MACHINE (AN ALLEGORY)

Putting it simply, we consider that the human society is advancing to a high level of mechanical sophistication, while, at the root of its own being, most of its problems remain unsolved. In ethical and spiritual terms, it can even be argued that the contemporary man is as poor, or even more, than his ancestors, all the way down to the point where History begins. This argument is not drawn from the fortunate and obvious advances that were done, theoretically, in some fields, such as the Human Rights. Nevertheless, in terms of the deep inadequacy regarding the adaptation to the whole (life force or world seen as a living system), it is clear that the present life style of the so-called developed world, is most dangerous, wasteful and destructive. For the purpose of illustrating our point of view, we will draw a parallel between what is being

⁴² These points will be discussed in greater detail further ahead.

done to the whole in general and a simple and common machine, like a *car*. We will compare those things that, in our opinion, are mechanical — such as institutions, organisations, states, and taxonomic learning — to an ordinary machine. We will assume, as has been shown along the previous pages of this dissertation, that the construction of our present reality is like a sophisticated engine. This goes all the way from the modes of function of institutions, organisations, states, Education — to the physical apparatuses that surround our life, and on which we are dependent, like cities or technological gadgets.

We can say that the car, our chosen example, is a direct materialisation of human thought and invention. We can say that it is *thought made matter*. Conversely matter, the car as direct product of thought, influences this same thought, in an Oroboros-like cycle. This machine alters the perception of reality, of speed, of movement — and deeper, possibly, at other unknown levels. And, presently, it is felt that this machine is increasing speed. It is felt that the machine is going faster and faster. As happens with cars, the faster they go, the riskier they are, so as a defence, the more sophisticated they become — but the more sophisticated they become, they faster they also go.

In order to make them safer, ABS brakes were invented and introduced; the same with lateral bars; airbags; on-board computer; electronic injection, etc, etc. This is like the action of reform that we see in our society. The intention is good, but parallel to the research to make these machines safer, there is an irresistible temptation to make them faster and more powerful — while it is known that the higher the speed, naturally higher the risk. So, on the one hand we have those that contribute for the *development* of this machine — be it by reforming it in order to make it safer; or by a Faustian passion for the power and sense of creation that can be brought out of manipulating it. On the other hand, we have some sort of modern Luddites that try to destroy, make it crash, not being aware of their own involvement in the actual state of affairs. In some sense, our society is *inside a progressively speeding machine*, our society is an enormous machine — and *inside* that moving machine, we have those who make it more sophisticated, who add more seat-belts, more airbags, more this and that, while others do not resist to increase its speed. And together with all of these, we still have

some others who — being, as well, inside this machine that *is rolling* very fast — are trying to exert violence, make something vital explode — or shoot and kill, for example, the driver on service.

In our opinion is not a question of reforming, of adding, of accelerating — or destroying while rolling at great speed. Somehow there should be the capacity of being able to *stop it for a moment*, stop for an instant *to measure, to meditate*⁴³ upon the consequences, to enable room for an alternative action. In our opinion, what counts for a balance of the whole, at this stage, is not to be found *in* the machine, in the *progressing* and *developing* of it, but in an evolution, a *regenerative* mutation that necessarily has to take other paths — a change, a *something* with the quality of the new. Something that represents ability to learn, *to discover something new, to bring about a creative response to the present challenge* — and *not* just to add more of the same — or to destroy⁴⁴...

3.1. THE ENGINEERING OF SUBJECTS, The 3rd, 4th and 5th SETS OF PROPOSITIONS

Having written about how the construction of a progressing machine is brought about, and the correlative clenching of an iron law of oligarchy, at a macro-level, we will now advance some more propositions, which will lead to the discussion of how this mechanisation makes for the engineering of subjects themselves. In this point of the dissertation we would like the reader to check the five points that we raised in the beginning (Structural Questions), before advancing to the new sets of propositions.

⁴³ *Measure* comes from the Latin *medire*. This is a fundamental concept in our dissertation. Interestingly, the root of this word is the same as of the words *meditation* (to reflect, to ponder, to give attention); and *medicine* (to maintain the right psycho-somatic measure, the sane balance and harmony in the organism). The right measure is, thus, connected with the attentive reflection (meditation) of reality as it is; and the sane balance of the dynamically inter-related elements of the complex system as a whole (medicine). In Greek tragedies, the catastrophe (Mautner: 2000: 88) represents the break of this same, subtle measure. In this sense, the tragedy is the consequence of breaking, disrespecting, ignoring the *right measure, the inner order of each and all interrelated things*.

⁴⁴ As was repeated several times by I. Fagerling throughout the seminars of the *Education and Development* course, given at IIE, Stockholm University, 2001, “what we have to learn is how to live with each other”. Such a statement clearly shows, that whatever action, whatever response given by us as individuals and societies, this action will have to take into primary consideration *the relation with the whole*.

Third set of propositions:

- A further step in the *progressive mechanisation* is the engineering of passive subjects⁴⁵ as bundles of different products, collectable fragments.
- The subject seen as a passive recipient (a consumerist)⁴⁶, and as an engineered product *in itself*. This product being, mainly, a self-concerned one.
- Education as one of these products that contribute for the engineering to the subject.

Forth set of propositions:

- Engineering of subjects as a process that leads to passivity, inner emptiness and boredom. Resulting from the habit of being lead, taught, the subject feels no creativity, no personal discovery springing from within his own person.
- Passivity, inner emptiness and boredom seen as promoting causes for destructive forms of transgression. Transgression seen as discharges of inner tension caused by inability to create and discover, i.e., to live life as the art of learning.

Finally, regarding the 4th and last chapter we will advance the following set (the fifth) of propositions:

Fifth set of propositions:

- Learning as art.
- Art as creation beyond the mechanical (as the *something else*, besides the initial set of elements).
- Learning as the art of the relevant, the adequate. Learning as the art of the right measure.

3.2. TEACHING FOR COMSUMERISTS

⁴⁵ Subject as opposed to “individual”. See proposal for the term *individual*, note 11

⁴⁶ To be taught, lead, civilised, saved, etc.

All is done for the subjects of our present society. The elements of the affluent societies are the passive buyers of the products that solve their daily lives. Most elements of these societies are nearly not unable to do a single thing by themselves. They are not self-reliant and they are incapable of self-help. There is neither physical nor psychological emancipation or independence (Vaneigem: 1996: 77,9). From birth to death all is provided as an institutionalised service (Ilich: 1971: chap.4). Everything is a good to be bought.

It can be asked why is it that the elements of our societies, instead of being taught fragments of knowledge, do not learn what is needed in order to be emancipated? Instead of being made consumerists, why is there no learning about how to deal with their own bodies (to prevent disease and, if necessary, how to cure them); how to fix their own goods, etc., how to be self-reliant? From food, to health, technology, education, physical security — one is dependent on alien expertise and power, having to pay the first and depend upon the other. In this sense, lacking autonomy, one is totally dependent on what one buys. Consequently the relationship with society is one of dependence, habit or forced co-operation (in order to get what one needs), instead of one of free participation. Being autonomous, self-sufficient, one would be able to know and decide when to co-operate and when *not* co-operate. But, mostly, things are designed in such a way that one cannot (or does not know how) not to co-operate.

In some sense this might seem exaggeration, due to the fact that, fortunately, some of us live in democratic societies. There is a sense of co-operation due to the fact that people seem to share the same basic wishes. However, regarding this one can ask: is there a real democracy, a diverse and harmonic order — or a consensus of self-interests, brought about by a moulding of peoples' interests to a converging vector⁴⁷?

⁴⁷At this point we would like to advance a distinction between two forms of order. We also pretend with this distinction of different types of order, to make a parallel with human communities/systems of relationships. The first one will correspond to the creative, holistic order. The second will correspond to the order resulting from a convergence of self-related, or egotistical, interests. The first type of concept of order we will call a *fractal order*, which is opposed to the second one that we will call a *carcinogenic order*.

Finding ways to fulfil all the subjects wishes and wants: is that the way to bring about peace and order in society? If so, it could, then, be argued that if these wishes and dreams were all the same, equal and standardised, they would be easy to cope with. Considering, now, for example youth, it can be pointed out that this has become a consumerist class, *par excellence*. In order that the demands of this consumerist class match what is being offered, this class has to have been "educated" in a way that its desires and demands all become the same. Therefore we can observe that youth across the globe (at least in affluent societies) is becoming very similar, isomorphic. Youth is becoming increasingly alike. They all consume the same and they all *want* to consume the same, thus they all end up eating the same, and so on.

Consumerism acts as an identity-construction (Lewis: 1980; Bell: 1976), which brings about the promotion of self-related, self-concerned values. In a big-scale isomorphic society, the search for an identity, for the construction of an "identity", and a sense of "individual" is greatly felt. As a substitute for the "individual", self-interest, self-concerned values are exploited. The ideal "self" (both in exterior image and

The first order, the *fractal* one is to be understood as an implicate, interconnected order which results in the good, and harmonic well-being of the whole. The whole seen as a complex organic system, where the small-scale patterns are mirror and mirrored on a big scale, in ever different but self-similar patterns (Gleik: 1988: 228-40). In chaos theory terms this can be conceived as a dynamic pattern, a fluid mosaic or *mandala* of human inter-related communities/systems, whose individuals are devoted to the well-being of the whole. This is an order born from the very ground of living force, beyond self-interest, self-concern, a force that harmonises the complex and dynamic whole, as can be observed in the universe. An order lived now by now in the fertility of the unpredictable — the challenging and mutational chaos that keeps the universe alive through its intrinsic "inventiveness" (Reeves: 1992: 9). (According to scientists, such as Feynman and Reeves, the universe renews itself through a continuous response to the challenge of the unpredictable. Universal collapse and universal death are always diverted, sometimes in a most critical moment, by an unpredictable, creative event that nobody could have foreseen or guessed. This inventiveness is observed regarding certain phases that the universe and the planet earth have gone through and which almost meant universal death (Reeves: 1992: 7-12).

In contrast, the *carcinogenic order* is an order resulting of organised self-interest, self-concern, defensiveness, parasitism and plundering (see the BBC documentary on cancer: *Superhuman, The Enemy Within*, Produced and Directed by Dinah Lord & Kate Barker, Executive Producer Michael Mosley, BBC Science, London MM). In terms of human systems, it stands for the fragmentary order that is born from particular structures, ideologies, institutions and massive passivity and alienation. Cancer order is an order that corrupts the whole in an (ultimately self-destructive) attempt for supremacy. Such a type of order has the logic of states and ideologies, it is a power struggle within the boundaries of particular, separate and self-centred interests. Interests ignorant and dissociated from the well-being of the whole. It lacks the perception of the interdependent, implicate nature of the system. This order can be seen in the organised nature of gangs, guerrillas, sports teams, nationalities, sects, lobbies, parties, governments and Mafia. It is an order resulting from, provisory, matching and converging interests, opposed to the well-being of the whole. It is a predatory order blind to the consequences of its actions both in the whole and the particular.

psychological content) is sold as the result of a combination of multiple purchasable products (Crane: 1992: 37). People are their own engineers, acting both as moulder and moulded material. People are to be seen as supermarket/warehouse recipients to be filled with different combinations of products, products with different prices, and even from different shelves — but all coming from the same place. Even for those who find themselves against the system, there is a misfit niche where to fit, and where to buy. Similarly as to the "alternative" section in music mega-stores — there is also for those who feel themselves somewhat *alternative*, a place that accommodates them, a moulding form that contributes for the construction of their self (Marshall: 1993: 137). All this for a price, of course.

In the past, there was the dependency of the body upon the machine. Nowadays there is psychological dependency on the consume-machine for the survival of the “self”. This self-construction and engineering is intimately related with the question of the *image* — the image that the self has of itself — and the needs for the perpetuation of that self-image (Abercrombie & Longhurst: 1998: 92). These needs are all, needless to say, self-concerned.

The image that is sold as ideal product, as ideal “self”, contains this interesting paradox: the image has to be something "original", "new" and somehow "unique" for each subject who buys it (Abercrombie & Longhurst: 1998: 33, 177). This urge for novelty allows the product to be very perishable, ephemeral and continuously reformed (within a very repetitive frame, obviously), which means business. This product is everything, from clothes, technology, education and life experiences. It has to seem very new, progressive and unique — but here lies the paradox: it is merely part of a very repetitive establishment. It is the norm, always the norm. Because, there is a paradoxical need to be original, *distinguished* while simultaneously being recognised, accepted and integrated by the surrounding community (Abercrombie & Longhurst: 1998: 116). Distinction and safety simultaneously — the protagonist’s fever (Pereira Bastos: 2001: 22). The subject feels himself as an "individual" while conforming to a circumscribed position in a larger or narrower spectrum of limited possibilities. The system is always shifting, though it is, very much the same thing in a mechanical and kaleidoscopic manner.

The over-stimulated hunger for new products, new reforms, new technologies has its parallel in people's own conception of their personal life. The inner emptiness, the lack of individuality, together with a sense of isolation, separation — the anonymity, disposability of everything, including people — boosts this need of fulfilment, of discovering, of getting hold of something new. This reveals a need for discovery, for learning and being surprised. However, even for that, there is also a market of mass education, mass religion, mass tourism, mass culture, extreme sports, mega-concerts and festivals — a mass standardisation that goes all the way down to the point of even constructing and dictating what is the correct image of a love relationship — and sexual life (Foucault: 1977: 306). Experiences are standardised, predictable, endemic and purchasable.

The same thing is happening with learning and education. The multitude of courses does not imply real novelty — but still contains an inner structure of repetition, shallowness and lack of creative spirit. Education is a norm, everybody, one way or another, ends up learning the same things in the same way (Llewellyn: 1997: chap. 2). The general level is low due to the weight of the machine. And it does not hide its price: submission, adaptation and conforming to *what is expected to be done*, either by the students or the teachers. The roles are defined and their acceptance is the price that the subjects willingly pay, because here also this product contributes for the safe construction of the “self”. The fear of “flunking”, of repeating, of being cast away, of being excluded from the collective, is too big and too menacing for the subject's image of himself (Llewellyn: 1997: 18). Besides the fear of being isolated, the fear of being poor is one of the biggest that any member of an affluent society can face. And education touches both those points — how can one person organise his life; meet other people, not be isolated, if not going to school, university, etc.? (Llewellyn: 1997: Intro.) How can one have a good monetary subsistence (besides through marginal and suspicious means) and a cultivated life, if not through formal Education?

So, we have said that consumerism makes for the constitution of the contemporary “self”⁴⁸, and that one of the main products for the engineering of that

⁴⁸ The consumerism-dependence of products, fashion or experiences makes for the construction, the engineering of a subject by the means of objectifying the entity as a sophisticated product/bundle. Bundle

“self” is, nowadays, Education. It contributes to the ritual of self-assurance, security and a notion of status (within a taxonomic framework) of the “self”, but definitely *not* to knowledge⁴⁹ — or intelligence, or sensitivity⁵⁰.

Focusing on education, education is not a way to learn how to be autonomous, but how to conform to the norm. It is a science of passivity (Llewellyn: 1997: 31-56). The formula of this product, which is bought at high prices, and which contributes for the engineering of subjects, has a main target which, here, metaphorically, we will call the *nomadic spirit*⁵¹. Together with other big institutions, the tendency of schools is to fixate, to trace a path, too keep surveillance, to pin down the precise location of the individual — and of his mind. This in order to build up a registry, to write down a historiography, a profile of the individual through the well defined, and *already invented* stages of his life. Like in the Elizabethan times, when there was the concept of a chain of beings (Tillyard: 1976: chap. 4), in the present society we have a taxonomic

on which people, paradoxically, become dependent and defend with all their energy — because this bundle is their own constructed “self”, the image that people have of themselves. Thus they defend it, contribute for its active engineering and hardening layers of identity — in an addictive process. The product/bundle is a concept, an image, even a *feeling of a “me”*, thing which, naturally, people defend as their innermost value (see Abercrombie & Longhurst :1998: 33).

⁴⁹ A recent and upsetting research shows that *the more students go to school the less they read. And if they read — the more they read, the more it is Stephen King...* For very interesting and clarifying research data on this issue check: Baudelot & Cartier (June 1998): *Lire au Collège et au Lycée, De la Foi du Chabonnier à Une Pratique Sans Croyance*, in Actes de la Recherche en Sciences Sociales, number 123.

⁵⁰ Programs like Big Brother, etc. were invented and produced in the so-called developed and educated countries. The problem is not only that they were invented there, but also that, they have top audiences amongst the educated and developed people of these same countries.

⁵¹We are extremely interested in drawing a parallel between the nomadic spirit and the spirit that animates art itself. Also we see a parallel of the two previous things with learning. So, *learning is to be understood, according to our view, as a nomadic art*. As inspiring reference, we have in mind the artist Richard Long. According to him, art is defined as a nomadic process, as a walk into the unknown (Beardsley: 1994: 75). As such, the work of art has as its means the walking movement (the continuum space-time) and the natural materials found along the way, stones, sand, clay, tree stubs, etc. This nomadic walk is itself a way of life because, as Long puts it, such walking is an art that humanises us, it is an art about “how to be a human being” (Furlong: 1994: 75). The nomadic art (also known in the U.S as Land Art) is seen as a participation, a direct experience, of the very order and process of nature. Art is not a *mimésis* (copy) but it is a creation, a performance, an active tautology of nature itself. In this sense, the nomadic walking is simultaneously the re-integration of man in nature — and the creation, by this same man, of an organic, living work of art within nature. Art is work of man, but man is part of nature, so *it is nature*, or the whole itself, that creates the work of art, having man as a medium. The work of art is such a thing that involves the artist’s body, his mind and the whole of the environment. The artist uses the material, that something alive, something part of an interrelated whole, respecting its significance and the form that it took in that very concrete situation (Burger: 1993: 119). Art is an environmental performance, it is contemplation in movement, an action that expresses and includes the praxis and the itinerary of the work of art itself (Codognato: 1994: 17). Art is then this nomadic walk, this exploration into new territory — allied to an investigative, creative mind.

caste of subjects, a value gradation according to the hierarchy of knowledge, modernity, sophistication.

The nomadic spirit is hit by institutions in general, and Education in particular, in three fronts. These are fronts of control over:

- 1) The *space*, 2) the *time*, and 3) the *mind*.

Considering Education, we should start by reminding the reader, that it is compulsory, so exposition to it, in developed societies, should be seen as nearly unavoidable. So, time is controlled by the schedules, by the extension of hours spent doing something⁵², by habit and routines. Within the daily ritual of the habitual, space is controlled due to tracking down of the movement. Repetition of actions, repetition of places, repetition of routes, together with specific people that belong to the same hierarchy, to the same class. Physically, bodily, there is a continuous allocation in space and time⁵³.

However, the contents of this time and space are not innocent, obviously. There is a program, a curriculum⁵⁴ — a set of tasks, of codes, a field of knowledge that is supposed to be incorporated, *accommodated*⁵⁵. And assessing such accommodation, there is a continuous evaluation, categorisation and examination going on. There is a constant occupation of the mind, there is always some drill going on — a mapping of the fields of knowledge that the mind has to traverse. There is always something to be done, something to hand in, some homework, some stage to complete — a continuous

⁵² Like, for instance, virtual learning (or learning by distance, via net): one way of evaluating the student, and attributing the certificate, is by the number of hours that he spends in front of the computer, time which is measured by the means of, for example, ticking down boxes with control questions along the way.

⁵³ If we think of a 15 year old youngster, on a Monday in October the 16th, 11:45 we will consider as a very strong probability that he is inside a classroom having 9/10th grade class.

⁵⁴ “What knowledge is of most worth?” (Apple: 1990: vii). This is a very complex question and, certainly, not a pacific one. For a detailed analysis on the “curriculum issue” and its connection with mechanisms of hegemony, see: Apple, M. (1990): *Ideology and Curriculum*, Routledge, New York and London.

⁵⁵ We remind the reader of the well-known distinction that Piaget (1956) made between *accommodation* (imitation, conforming) and that other process, that is *assimilation*. To the second one is, generally, given less importance. However, in intelligence, it is assimilation that is the one of primary importance. Such a process represents the total digestion, the learning of something in such a way that it becomes one with the person, who has *understood* it — and has not simply reproduced it.

*progressing forward*⁵⁶. Learning is substituted for being led. Innocence is substituted with belief, with the solid establishment of a rigid perception of reality. This makes the mind conform and submit. In the case of children, with the passing of years, the subtlety, the curiosity, interest and joyful energy that was characteristic in their spontaneous learning process, seems to wither. Knowledge takes the primary position in what is considered being educated, which means: an articulate accumulation of information and data. “Learning” is thus seen as the mechanistic and efficient speed-ability of retaining and reproducing knowledge within a narrow field of different combinations.

Thought itself is, thus, always being stimulated and provoked from the exterior. Like learning is confused with being taught, teaching is confused with pushing and forcing people in the right direction. Most education is the transplantation of alien, pre-established knowledge, and not a discovery, something learned by the individual himself. As the subject is not supposed to wander around freely, as he is not supposed to adventure himself into the unknown, as he is not supposed to have an own path — as there is no nomadic spirit in learning and Education, because that is impossible to examine and evaluate — the subject is pinned down to a spot, a time and a class, being exposed to a structured program. As he cannot move, as he is an empty recipient, a passive spot where something is being transplanted, as he is all that instead of a searching nomad — no doors can be pointed out for him, so that he himself does the walking through them. Instead, he is told about what is on the other side — of *some* of these doors. And he is also told that *someone else* has already done the walking, through them, for him. And it is this authority, the discovery of *that someone else*, which he will have to accommodate as his own. Another product, something already made, that the subject will consider his own. This is what we mean by consumerism.

Definitely, in our culture, society and Education there is no cultivation of sane idleness — the art of doing nothing, thinking nothing⁵⁷ — allowing space for something other, than the already known, to *possibly* flourish. There is neither

⁵⁶ There are enforced tasks in order not to fail or fall back. Or there is the impulse to attain something better, be promoted, get higher degrees, climb the career ladder, etc.

⁵⁷ We have noticed that together with the fear of poverty, boredom and doing-nothing, are some of the perspectives that most distress people.

cultivation of sensitivity, nor is the sensitivity already present allowed to survive. Sensitivity that is destroyed under so much passive stimulation, under so much informational noise — suffocated under too much knowledge. Sensitivity that gains no roots because it is allowed so little *ataraxia*⁵⁸.

This habit of being continuously physically placed, of being continuously situated in terms of time, of being continuously lead, taught, examined⁵⁹, exposed to authoritative, curricular knowledge is what, in our opinion, makes for passivity and dependence. This all-pervasive structuring of life obviously gives, psychologically, a sense of security through its ever-renewed rituals of predictability — like those to which one becomes increasingly attached, as one is becoming senile⁶⁰. (Senility seen as when the mind, divorced from its strength, unable to regenerate and to adventure, treads over and over the same old tracks, repeating the same stiff routines where it feels safe).

Summing up, as we have been pointing out, the engineering of subjects is a process that also results from a taxonomic science of continuous placing, fixation, and categorisation. This is done at the level of the body — through the various structures that place, constrain, and design routes for it; and at the level of the mind — through the contents that are transmitted, taught to the subject while physically constrained. This amounts to passivity, inner emptiness and boredom in the subjects — the atrophy of the nomadic spirit. Also, this is where consumerism comes in. Consumerism is a dependence of the subject upon exterior elements that nurture *an image*, in fact the result of a bundle of products (from fashion, to knowledge) — and which he takes for his identity. All this due to the fact that the subject has no autonomy, no individuality — no inner creativity — *that* independent fire that lives of its own intensity.

So, 1) the tension caused by the mechanic life style; plus 2) consumerism and the habit of being inwardly dependent on exterior elements that lead the way; plus 3)

⁵⁸ It is astonishing how the Greeks, materially so poor and with so little knowledge in comparison to our present standards, were able to have such deep insights into the reality. *Ataraxia* means unperturbed serenity, peace of mind. It can be compared to the state of *samadhi*, which in eastern philosophies represents the awakened energy of intelligence or wisdom. According to Epicureans, *ataraxia* is “the essential ingredient in happiness, the most desirable state of human existence” (Mautner: 2000: 48).

⁵⁹ Which, through the measuring of success, can turn out to be a subtle form of self-assurance of one before himself, and comparatively, before others.

⁶⁰ As is stated in the *Paideia*: “Stability is not a secure sign of health, because it also reigns in the conditions of senile rigidity, in the agonising moments of a culture” (Jaeger: 1995: 4)

the inner emptiness and boredom resulting from that, pile up in two interwoven things: addiction and need of transgression (Vaneigem: 1996: 11-21, 26), which will be dealt with next.

3.3. PASSIVITY AND TRANSGRESSION

The inability of *discovering*, allied to the drilled habit of being taught, orientated and occupied by school and society, has made the sense of inner emptiness⁶¹ and boredom in youth even more acute (Vaneigem: 1996: 16). Everything is external input — very little is non-taught, very little is learning resulting of inner flourishing and creation. This input-dependency and passivity, consequently, brings about a barren feeling of inward sterility⁶².

This emptiness and boredom results in a demand for passive stimulation and entertainment which turns, itself, into a form of addiction. The incapacitating habit of expecting to be given, to be lead, to be saved, to be taught is, as pointed out before, at the core of our present consumerist society. And, obviously, when something has to be massively distributed, vulgarised, its quality goes down.

Let us take as an example mass culture/education. Clearly it is designed to be 1) simple in content, easy to understand and as catchy as an advertisement. 2) Fast in speed of change, consummation and treatment of topic. (The informational overdose and race that every year teachers and students have to go through in order to finish the program; films with short blunt dialogues; almost no political discussion and debate in

⁶¹ “In technologically advanced countries of Europe and America, many people feel this sort of emptiness and commit suicide. The reason they kill themselves is not because they have no food, or cannot economically or moralistically get along with other members of society. They commit suicide because they have lost the reason for living and feel this existential emptiness. Nowadays, even some elementary or junior high school students try to commit suicide. I am afraid that they feel the same existential emptiness. Though not many of them go as far as to kill themselves, young people in today’s Japan have become indifferent and have lost enthusiasm for anything. I think existential emptiness is the underlying reason for this phenomenon. The richer we become materially, the more we lose our reason for living and feel emptiness spiritually. This kind of existential emptiness cannot be cured by developing contrivances for daily living or by technological civilisation. (Uchiyama: 1995: 152)

⁶² Much of the discussion done in these lines is result of direct observations and private conversions between us and drug-addicts, problematic students and delinquents. Most of these discussions were had within school context and others in suburban slums, where we used to do social work.

television; etc.) 3) Emotive, in order to arouse easy emotions and feelings that are neither subtle nor rational. Intensity is lived through low quality means⁶³.

There is clearly a culture of the infantile. "Learning" equals passive instruction, exposition and preferably it should be something easy, entertaining. It is neither supposed to demand sacrifice, search, commitment, nor involvement and self-denial⁶⁴. Just accommodation. Information and knowledge are, themselves, fragmented and inarticulate factoids, infotainment, easy to swallow due to its entertaining and passive quality⁶⁵.

In its turn, the mass culture machine promotes (with its violence, simplicity and emotionality) tension and restlessness which can only be appeased by strong discharges of emotion, speed and excitement, provided by this same machine. Hard-disco music and thriller films are good example of the workings of this mass-culture machine of which youth is so much part. These products are solely capable of being craved, searched for, purchased and appreciated by stressful, anxious subjects. These products provide pleasure solely to subjects that are under these states of tension. Pleasure is in this case, definitely, associated with such stress and tension — and its sporadic, planned instants of discharge and consequent relieve — specially through the means of drugs⁶⁶ and violence. Interestingly, the dependency created in these moments of discharge makes the subjects dependent on states of tension and anxiety in order to relieve

⁶³ The human mind needs to feel intensity, it needs to be aware of the energy-movement of life. Nevertheless, in our passive and sedentary culture, the only way to feel intensity is mainly through the means provided by mass culture. As Pereira Bastos (2001: 22) puts it: "What the human mind searches for is intensity, any intensity, and all intensities can be substituted. Some television programs give such a feeling of intensity that people feel extraordinarily attracted to them. (...) The search of this intensity is a mental question. The brain and the nervous system search different degrees of intensity. If it is given by cocaine, alcohol, extreme sports, joy rides, gambling, or sex, it does not matter".

⁶⁴ "First, students' capacities for learning - their abilities to concentrate and to work on a project over a period of time — have been eroded by the pervasive influence of our passive consumer culture. Increasingly, consumption of goods and entertainment is a dominant attribute of our life style. Instant gratification — with little or no concentration or effort - is only as far away as the telephone, TV remote or shopping mall. Students are growing in a world where it has become a virtue to want it all and want it now! Why read a novel when there is MTV? Why work over a period of time when you could be playing Nintendo? In such a world students' capacities for sustained concentration atrophy, like unused muscles. Often, when they are asked to do harder but more challenging work, they don't know how to begin."(Wagner: 1994: 56)

⁶⁵ Course given by Samoff at Sida, April 2001

⁶⁶ Coherently we are considering alcohol a drug.

them⁶⁷. This addiction for tension makes, obviously, for insensitivity. As we have pointed out before⁶⁸, the greater the stimulation, the greater the insensitivity resulting from it. Through a sort of twisted logic, we can point out the following equation:

Inner emptiness and tension demands for discharge (Vaneigem: 1996: 25-35). This discharge is felt as pleasure (pleasure understood as the relief from tension). This discharge, this pleasure, is attained by means of further addictive stimulation (drugs, violence, emotionality, speed, etc.) *which increases further insensitivity, further tension and passivity*. Passivity and inner emptiness demand stimuli — so, the circle closes, and the next cycle begins. Such is the *routine*.

Meditating upon what might be the cause of our society's "creative and artistic impotence", Herbert Read, in his famous work for UNESCO says:

The first [cause] is the general phenomenon of alienation, the essence of which is the progressive divorce of human faculties from natural processes, which might be described as the atrophy of sensibility. If the seeing and handling, touching and hearing, and all the refinements of sensation (...) are not educated and trained from birth to maturity the result is a being that hardly deserves to be called human: a dull-eyed, bored and listless automaton whose one desire is for violence in some form or other — violent action, violent sounds, distractions of any kind that can penetrate to its deadened nerves. (Read/UNESCO: 1969: 33)

Society, as we know it, is constructed upon this addictive mechanism of tension-relief. Addiction does nothing but reflect to the highest intensity the nature of tension-relief, craving and fulfilment, for which society, with its enslaving authority and control methods, is the most sophisticated and massive expression. (Mottram: 1971: 16, 55). The classroom conflict and transgression — or the Friday night binge of most of big civilised cities, is a good representative of the strain and tensions that accumulates within the fabric of our schools, offices and cities during the week spent there.

The structural tension present in our societies leads to a permanent disruption in the flow of events, as it is observable in classrooms where a great pacifying ability is

⁶⁷ For interesting discussion on addiction and contemporary culture see the documentary: *The Art of Tripping*. Presented by Bernard Hill. A Jon Blair Film Company. Production for Channel 4. MCMXCIII

⁶⁸ See note 19.

needed in order to bring about an easy and relaxed atmosphere of inquiry and interest. As it is known, most of the time in school is a waste of energy, a perpetual conflict where no work is done. At a social level, this same tension has problematic consequences: adults, for example, exclude themselves from active participation in many fields of life, such as the education of their own children or the destinies of their societies. Most people, by the end of the day, are so worn out that they prefer to come home, sit down and watch television — and get indoctrinated (Achbar&Wintonick: 1992) ⁶⁹. With youth, the problem related with the culture of the infantile is visible. In terms of social engagement, in terms of learning about our world and its problems, the youth of today is very far from making use of the enormous freedom of thought and action, that is at its reach, in order to face and solve these same problems. Despite all its problems, we have the conviction that there is room in our society to put questions, to inquire and even to re-invent it. However, curiously, the opposed direction is the one preferred. There is a clear option for escapism, for not facing reality, and for not even trying to change it. This escapism is clearly expressed by the great interest shown for altered states of consciousness, for the addiction to toxic products, from hard drugs to alcohol — or for the intensity caused by violence, transgression⁷⁰. It is pointless to refer to the alarming number of young people that, these days, is dependent on one or another drug.

Presently in society, there is a clear blockage and a consequent explosive dispersion of energy. Physically and psychologically, there is a great inner tension due, as we have been demonstrating, to the rigidity, routine, repetition and habits that the body and brain go through. The growing inability to learn, to *grow inwardly*⁷¹ — the feeling caused by the conditioning state in which subjects fall, causes, even if only unconsciously, great frustration tension.

By the means of transgression, alcohol, violence, drugs and strong emotions, there is a sudden discharge of this blocked energy, of this tension. The relief caused by

⁶⁹ *Manufacturing Consent. Noam Chomsky And Media*, by Mark Achbar and Peter Wintonick. Necessary Illusions in Co-production with Board of Canada, 1992

⁷⁰ This discussion, with its general background on the nature of addiction and drugs, is especially in debt to Bockris (1982: 111); Mottram (1971: 118); and Burroughs (1993: Introduction).

⁷¹ See the deep connection between the importance of knowing oneself, the process of inner growth, and the concept of education of the Greek man, in Werner Jaeger's *Paideia*.

the sudden outburst of tension is felt as pleasure (Mottram: 1971: 118). Altered states, states of alienation, are seen and felt as pleasure. And these forms of pleasure are, themselves, purchasable products that, in controlled and surveyed forms, are given to people. Transgression is a very carefully studied market, as well as pornography, violence — alcohol and other legal and illegal drugs. So, what we are pointing at is that, society, in order to be able to sustain such an omnipresent system of allocation, routine and repetition had, necessarily to include room for transgression into the system — an allowed and controlled transgression. A space of transgression that co-habits in perfect and pacific contradiction with the rest of the society⁷².

Through the means of allowed and controlled transgression the subject's energy although temporarily relieved is, of course, dispersed and lost, rendering the subject more vulnerable. The continuous state of hangover caused by various forms of stimulation represents also an increasing dependency⁷³. This, progressively, results in a further weakening of the subject and an increasing inability to find his own way, i.e., to learn how to use the enormous amount energy available in the body and brain without letting it build up as accumulated tension. The mechanism of addiction is correlated with the progressive state of weakness and passivity in which the subject falls together with an increasing dependency on the elements that provoke the discharge of tension. Conversely, it is also possible to it from the opposite angle: the subject's increasing dependence on what gives the feeling of discharge is proportional to his increasing passivity. By this we draw a parallel between passivity and transgression, — and

⁷²Such societies are fragmented, not whole, presenting an inner contradiction to its members (especially the young) between what is *told* and what is *done* — between the *tell* and *show*. Just to give an example: Children, at school, are *told* that they should be pacific, tolerant, respectful with women, etc. But, what they are, in fact, shown at home, in television, magazines, street advertisement, etc., is the glorification of violence; the cultivation of the sexy-and-beautiful in opposition to the nerd-and-uninteresting; the perpetuation of women as sex objects; etc. This means a self-contradictory society, where learning is not a holistic process — a process, resulting from everything all the time, sprung from a society that is whole, coherent — but a process of selection and judgement. In such conditions, and allied to the overwhelming quantity of informational noise, it is not strange to see that the selection which is done tends to what appeals to the most basic interests and appetites.

⁷³ As is known, the hangover feeling is a sign of the body craving for more of the addictive substance — one method to relieve, for example, an alcohol hangover is by the intake of *more* alcohol.

correlative *insensitivity and alienation*.⁷⁴ They are both born from the same machine. A machine of which massive standardised education is part.

4. LEARNING AS THE ART OF THE *RIGHT MEASURE*

As we have been pointing out, the *progressing machine*, in which the present system of Education is such an important cog, makes for a process of senility, addiction — alienation — at a macro-level, in society, and at micro-level, in the subject. Throughout this work, we have been doing a sort of zooming starting from the big structures (present in the institutions) towards the inner structures (present in the subjects). Due to such an approach and contingency it could, erroneously, be understood that the subjects are passive victims of overwhelming forces, totally alien to them. However, that would not be totally accurate. In fact we think that subjects are subjected, in great extent, to what they themselves invented, to the structures and mechanisms that their own thoughts brought about, in the first place. And if those structures and mechanisms are to be understood, such a process will have to begin *from the individual* — where, in a micro-scale, these same structures and mechanisms are mirrored. In this sense, the de-mechanisation of society has to have its source in the individual, in his awakened awareness, in his ability to learn how to recognise the structures that subject him, and go beyond the conditioning caused by them. No one can be waiting for someone else, or some reformed institutions, or whatever, to take such a daring step.

Now, up to this point of our work, we have seen that Education, in parallel with the general tendency of mechanisation of society, is itself, also, an isomorphic structure for the mechanisation of the individual. We do *not* see Education as 1) the creative and native fruit of its own soil, wherever this soil might be; 2) as a living system representing cultural diversity, i.e., everybody *not* learning the same things, through the

⁷⁴ *Alienation* as fragmentation, as estrangement from the participation in the whole, and consequent “objectification” of the individual (into a subject). Alienation as a separation, a rupture of the relation with one’s own body and environment. Alienation, also, as result from toxicity, addiction, etc. According to the definition in the *Oxford Dictionary of Sociology*, alienation comprises the “dimensions of powerlessness, meaninglessness, isolation (...)” and “estrangement is a consequence of social structures which oppress people, denying them their essential humanity (...) Alienation as a subjectively identifiable state of mind, involving feelings of powerlessness, isolation, and discontent at work —

means of the same repetitious structure, here, there and everywhere, 3) as the enabler of the evolution of individuals, opposed to a programmed engineering of subjects.

We have, also, seen that the educational system is not, in our opinion, related to *real learning*. Real learning implying discovery and freedom. Real learning that means bringing new insight into the crucial problems of our reality — such as violence, waste, inner emptiness or the general desensitisation of the members of our society.

But the question remains: what is *learning*? For such an impossible question we will point out a very broad direction, a very provisory set of propositions. These propositions are only, as the Zen saying goes, like a finger that points at the moon. It is, thus, important to remember that the finger *is not* the moon, but just a pointer. So finally, and regarding our last chapter we advance the following **fifth set of propositions**:

- Learning as art.
- Art as creation beyond the mechanical (as the *something else*, besides the initial set of elements).
- Learning as the art of the relevant, the adequate. Learning as the art of the *right measure*⁷⁵.

especially when this takes place within the context of large, impersonal, bureaucratic social organisations” (Marshall: 1998: 13-14)

⁷⁵ See note 43.

First of all and most importantly, these propositions, or any proposition about learning, should convey *the spirit of learning as that of an art*⁷⁶. Art that, like intelligence, is, then, the creation beyond the mechanical (the something else, besides the initial set of elements). In this sense learning, as an art, is the creative and mutational element, it is *the turning point* in one's views — it is the individual walk and entering into a new territory, with new eyes, and a new perception. Real learning has to be like art. Art that is the experimenting, the discovery, the daring step given by the individual. Art which is that something

eternally disturbing, permanently revolutionary. It is so because the artist, in the degree of his greatness, always confronts the unknown, and what he brings back from that confrontation is a novelty, a new symbol, a new vision of life, the outer image of inward things. His importance to society is not that he voices received opinions, or gives clear expression to the confused feelings of the masses (...) The artist is what the Germans call *ein Rüttler*, an upsetter of the established order. The greatest enemy of art is the collective mind, in any of its many manifestations. The collective mind is like water that always seeks the lowest level of gravity: the artist struggles out of this morass, to seek a higher level of individual sensibility and perception. (Read/UNESCO: 1969: 27)

And it is *each one* of these daring steps, *each one* of these new discoveries done by *each* individual that contributes to his assimilation into the whole of life. It is by being a free, creative individual that he is part of the whole. Because, the whole is intrinsically change, living mutation. In this sense, in order to address the flowing change, one has to deeply understand, deeply learn what is *going on*, and have an ever renewed, creative response. This action, this measure, will necessarily be unique, the right one — a new one. It is, then, obvious that, as a base, one cannot rely on what is past and accumulated, on the established structures and knowledge, on the predictable and mechanical responses, because what one is facing is new, *is change*, needing creativity as an answer. We will now proceed to clarify the nature of these statements in further detail:

⁷⁶ Regarding *learning and education as an art* see Husén & Postlethwaite (1994) Preface to the *International Encyclopedia of Education*, Second Edition. Vol.1. See also the articulation between art and the nomadic spirit & the nomadic spirit and learning in note 51.

As we have been demonstrating, addiction, senility makes for alienation of the individual from the whole, which means fragmentation. This is the epicentre of our broken-up society — it is the epicentre of conflict and self-related values. The conception and perception of reality that, presently, is reigning, is contributing to a large-scale destruction, to a further desensitisation, and divorce between the human, and all the rest of the nature and cosmos. However, *the actual* oneness and interrelation of the whole⁷⁷ should make us meditate and consider that something must be learned. That a step beyond the present and repetitive state has to be given — this taking into account that what happens to the one, implicates the whole. In this sense there is the individual responsibility of learning how *to be part*, how *to relate* with the whole. Any action and discovery of the one is catalytic for the whole. But... the way to be part of the whole *is not* through homogenisation, standardisation, normalisation... — but exactly, by going in the opposite direction.

The way to relate, to actively participate of life's *ágape*⁷⁸, is by being creative, by the renewed action of learning all the time — by being an active participator of life's creation, i.e., *by creating as well*. By being an “artist”, by living life, each gesture as a movement of art. This is the opposed posture of the one that leads to *passivity* (needing to be taught, lead); to *dependence* (upon what others do, thus losing one's individuality); and to *alienation* (becoming separated from the whole). Learning, just as art, is a creative action that demands energy, freedom, passion, emancipation — and that can only spring from one's own being. It cannot be bought or given. It has to be awakened by one's own intrinsic creativity.

And, as we have been implying, if this *whole* is to be pointed at in any way, that should be done through a metaphor. Metaphorically, the *whole can be seen as a creative and living flux, a process, whose essence is change* (Heraclitus: 1992: 6,18). The whole is like a river in which *not even* its substance is always the same. “Everything flows (*panta rei*), nothing persists, nothing continues the same” (Heraclitus: 1992: 6). It is related to what Confucius, while observing a river has said:

⁷⁷ Both the fractal order, seen in chaos, and the ocean-like relation between *everything*, as it is seen in quantum theory, are some of the observations that contemporary science is advancing.

“Everything flows on and on like this river, without pause, day and night. This expresses the idea of change”.⁷⁹ Reality in its whole is this movement and change, it is this *fundamental rhythm*. It is an “ever living fire kindling in measures and going out in measures.” (Heraclitus: 1992: 30)

In order to show the relevance of such statements we have, throughout this dissertation, pointed at the absolutely transient nature of reality and the futility, and inadequacy, that all big mechanic structures represent when they are the means of response to such ever-transforming nature. Besides, *even if* at moments they did respond, as Tristan Tzara states in the famous *Dada Manifesto* “every sort of construction converges into a boring sort of perfection, a stagnant idea of golden swamp” (Tzara: 1918: 1)⁸⁰. Nothing can be repeated. So, if there is something that is permanent in reality, it is its intrinsically *transient* nature. In this sense, the engineering of beyond-human-scale-machines, rigid and heavy buildings of repetition and authority not only goes against the most intimate nature of life, but contributes to the types of destruction that previously we have been dealing with⁸¹.

Regarding reality, whose essence is change, in order to make part (to participate) of such a dynamic whole and not make for further fragmentation (alienation), the individual has to be one with the unpredictable flux, the ever-renewed flow of events. So, it is clear that we are *not* talking about a progressive conception of life — of being inadequate now and hoping to develop towards becoming better — but one of continuous adaptation/creation, *right now*. This could be seen as a continuous

⁷⁸ From the Greek, meaning banquet.

⁷⁹ *I Ching*, p. *lv*

⁸⁰ “How can anyone hope to order the chaos that constitutes the infinite, formless variation: man?” (Tzara: 1918: 1)

⁸¹ It can even be argued that it contributes for a large-scale desensitisation of the creative dimension in the human being. “We may next ask, how does it come about that modern societies have become insensitive to the arts. The hypothesis that at once suggests itself is that this fundamental change is, in some sense to be determined, a consequence of the sudden increase in the size of societies, a development that accompanies the industrialisation of a country. It has always been a matter for wonder that the greatest epochs of art — Athens in the seventh and sixth centuries BC, Western Europe in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, the city-states of Italy in the fourteenth and fifteenth century — are associated with communities that, in comparison with the typical modern State, were minuscule. We tend to ignore this fact, to regard it irrelevant, and even to assume that the biggest and most powerful nations must naturally, in due course, produce the greatest art. It is a conclusion for which history offers no support”. (Read/UNESCO: 1969: 29) According to this line of thought it can be pointed that in massive, mechanised structures, as our society is, the creative spirit is lost because these structures fixate, predict and industrialise the human being within a pre-invented grid.

process of evolution, not towards something, but as a process of *being, right now, with the whole*.

This present tense evolution, this mutational spirit is, thus, the ability to be creative — the ability to bring into existence a new element — besides what is already there. The nomadic spirit, never fixing itself, evolving — adapting in a process of being with the whole — flows with the whole of movement. *The movement, the actuality being, itself, always new, demands an ever-renewed response*. It demands intelligence (a non-mechanistic response); creativity, which is the unpredictable mutation, the *something else* that — “out of the blue” and not being previously present — comes into being, as a novelty. Such artful ability is the *art of the right measure*, the adequate action, *hic et nunc*, in active present tense. In a whole universe of possibilities, right now, there is *such* right action that is adequate, that is relevant — and that *right measure*, that relevance and adequacy, that right gesture, is what shows the sensitivity of an artist, the creation of an individual.

So, what we have been saying is that: 1) learning (not accumulating knowledge) is an art; 2) as an art, learning is the art of the right measure; 3) the right measure being what is relevant and adequate. Conversely, in its turn, what is relevant and adequate comes into being with the learning of *what is*⁸², the here and now of this unique context, and how to act (or not) with it, according to situation, timing — and a myriad of other elements, dynamically related in a whole event. For this *it might* be necessary to apply what was previously learned/assimilated — but the *use*⁸³ of this knowledge is to be creative in itself, because the new instant and situation has totally different implications⁸⁴. In this sense, knowledge is not seen as a passive and accumulated

⁸² The learning of what is right in front our eyes. The ability to learn, with depth, *what is* the present, living, moving context. Because *what is* is movement, the flux. And by this we remind the reader of the unfortunate fact that when facing most situations that must be dealt with, people, countries, etc., apply a measure that worked elsewhere. They apply what was, in fact, the relevant and adequate measure *in another context*.

⁸³ *Not* the reproduction.

⁸⁴ This context might be a whole community, or a classroom. Thinking particularly about the classroom, it is absolutely clear that there has to be an ever-renewed and creative response to the challenge posed in that environment. Such response demands utmost sensitivity to the whole of the environment, exact timing and ability to *read between the lines of what is going on*. It does not matter how much one might

burden — a heavy loot, a bundle with value *per se* — but as a tool that comes into use according to the inspiration of the artist, according to the active relevance of the instant.

What we have pointing at in the previous paragraphs is at learning as a process of de-mechanisation, of de-alienation. Also, as a regenerative process that counteracts what we have termed as senility⁸⁵. Learning is seen as a process of assimilation, being something far beyond one of accommodation. And, simultaneously, the creative action of this learning, the application of *that* right and subtle measure, is what assimilates the individual into the whole. This art cannot be taught — just learned. It is the art of the individual — because it is something that has to be discovered/felt by him. Something that he has not been given, taught, forced or sold. It is a path that he himself walked. The surrounding environment provides the nurture, but the seed — the ability to learn, the passion to explore and enquire — that is what is not given by anyone. That is the living potential to be cherished, protected⁸⁶ — to be given strength and freedom, but which cannot be manufactured through any formula. Such a seed of attention, of creation, it is the daring sparkle of curiosity and joy — the nomadic spirit that we have seen⁸⁷ in the eyes of children — ready to adventure itself, to walk very far, if given the freedom. Such a seed is what is individual (not made up of parts, like pieces in an engine), undivided, whole in itself — but, simultaneously, universal, because, it is our conviction, that all have the creative potential to walk far, and discover much.

Learning is thus, the unimpaired observation, contemplation of the flowing reality, the deep *understanding* of its **rhythm** — and the adequate, relevant action, or non-action, which represents the right measure. So, the whole process is a subtle balance, like the harmony of tensions in a string instrument (Heraclitus: 1992: 32), or the creative intermingling note in the flow of music. Like a good musician, who participates of the musical flux, he is able to improvise the right note, or keep the right silence, just in the right moment. The right measure, simultaneously, assimilates him

have read of pedagogy, in a classroom situation there is a special feeling, a direct present tense creativity that has to act — many times surprisingly.

⁸⁵ The repetitive routes of bundled knowledge, inadequately, irrelevantly applied here and there, for this and that. Without the *right measure*.

⁸⁶ Education's role ought to be one of creation of a sane environment that allows *the spontaneous act of learning to learn what is relevant*. For a detailed discussion about the conditions of growth, i.e., the environment, and the learning potential, see note 21.

into the whole and makes manifest a knowledge that has been assimilated. A knowledge that is given a creative and intelligent expression by the one who uses it in *its right measure*. Not all the knowledge is applicable to every instant. Not all that is known is relevant all the time and everywhere. In the creative flux of reality there is the sober need to, firstly, apply *just* that which is relevant in each context (which demands an intelligent measuring and contemplation of each instant); and, secondly, to allow room for the improvising flow, the creative note that has never been played before, the daring exploration into the unknown, (which demands an artistic, a nomad spirit). As Heraclitus (1992: 9) puts it: “The repetition of one and only sound is not harmony. Harmony is made of difference. This harmony is precisely the absolute change, transforming itself.”

Naturally such a perception means the end of isomorphism. Continuously, here and there, now and then, things are a flux, creatively alive and in movement. Consequently, no blueprint, no structure can be imposed, transplanted, sold, proselytised, accepted, here, there and everywhere⁸⁸. Be it in the context of entire countries, or in the context of individuals. Besides, learning is a creative process, a holistic movement that lives through the active participation and relationship of individuals and a non-fragmented society and environment. Only through emancipated individuals and a society that is not exclusively concerned with self-related values, can a fluid, experimental and artful system of education come into being⁸⁹. An education, that like art “is the pattern evolved in a complex interplay of personal and societal processes of adjustment.” (Read/UNESCO: 1969: 29). An education that, in fact, points out doors to individuals that walk their own path and, opportunely, share their discoveries with the rest of the society. An Education that means real learning.

⁸⁷ Especially during our personal experience in teaching.

⁸⁸ “Analyses in the domain of education however, cannot be informed by questions about educational issues alone. In other words, any study of education policy must address first and foremost the fundamental and interlocking dynamics in the *context* within which education is operating at the given time. It also requires, especially in the light of the pervasiveness of globalisation, that scholars begin to address the equally pervasive but complex issue of the decline and disappearance of alternative conceptions of reality which could give rise to alternative policy frameworks.” (Odora: 1989: 1)

⁸⁹ Unfortunately, due to the present extension of this paper is not possible for us to present our views about such a hypothetical system.

5. CONCLUSION or TURNING POINT

“The Turning Point: After a time of decay comes the turning point. The powerful light that has been banished returns. There is movement, but it is not brought by force (...) thus the movement is natural, arising spontaneously. For this reason the transformation of the old becomes easy. The old is discarded and the new is introduced. Both measures accord with the time; therefore no harm results. Societies of people sharing the same views are formed. But since the groups come together in full public knowledge and are in harmony with the time, all selfish separatist tendencies are excluded, and no mistake is done.” *I Ching* p.97

Throughout this dissertation, what we mainly did was to bring up questions, and measure their implications. We started with the question of whether there is a *progressive machine* being globalised — engineering the world into an isomorphic system (under the clench of an iron law of oligarchy) where people are to be considered as objectified masses of consumerists. To this we have answered “yes”. The process that lead us to that answer went through the examination of several propositions, namely

- Development seen as a branch of a *specific globalisation* process.
- A *specific globalisation* seen as a new form of colonialism.
- Development, in this specific sense, seen as a new form of colonialism.
- Institutions and big mechanistic structures or systems (corporations, conglomerates, etc.) tend to isomorphism, corruption and senility.
- A specific globalisation process is mainly being driven and implemented by means of enormous institutions, corporations and structures.
- Such a globalisation process (and together with it, development and education) brought about through these means leads to isomorphism, corruption and senility.

The following question was whether education, as a system, is reproducing the same general tendency, being itself a standardised product to be sold — being something, in

most cases, inadequate, essentially the same here, there and everywhere. To this we have also answered “yes”.

We have also pointed out to the general features and structures of this education, defending that it reproduces the general tendencies of our consumerist society and we showed its connection with mechanisms of subject engineering. For that purpose we have structured a line of thought that had the following propositions:

- A further step in the *progressive mechanisation* is the engineering of passive subjects as bundles of different products, collectable fragments.
- The subject seen as a passive recipient (a consumerist), and as an engineered product *in itself*. Being this product, mainly, a self-concerned one.
- Education as one of these products that contribute to the engineering of the subject.

Examining the engineering of subjects, we considered it a process that leads to passivity, inner emptiness and boredom. Resulting from the habit of being lead, taught, the subject feels no creativity, no personal discovery springing from within his own person. And the consequent passivity, inner emptiness and boredom were seen as a promoting cause for destructive forms of transgression, with this transgression representing discharges of inner tension caused by the inability to create and discover.

At this point of our work we have questioned if the present educational system represents real *learning*? (Implying discovery, freedom — the bringing of new insight into the crucial problems of our reality, such as violence, waste, or inner emptiness). Regarding this question, our answer is that this present education, unfortunately, is not addressing what we consider what is most essential for our present society. As to the question of what learning then is, we decided to point out a very broad direction, in which learning would represent the artful ability of learning what is adequate, and applying *the* right measure that makes sense in the context or whole of which it is part. In order to discuss such a view we advanced the following set of propositions:

- Learning as art.

- Art as creation beyond the mechanical (as the *something else*, besides the initial set of elements).
- Learning as the art of the relevant, the adequate. Learning as the art of the right measure.

By means of this, we pointed at the fact that it is inadequate to create mechanisms beyond human-scale in order to face the challenges posed by life. Here and there, now and then — in this or that situation, the challenge is different, the infinite implications and non-linear variables have changed. *Are changing*. Life is movement and change, and the way to address its flux is definitely not through rigid formulas, gigantic structures — like the educational one — that are supposed to function all the time, everywhere. Because, *the only thing that functions is that which is relevant*, i.e., the adequate action that is correspondent, that matches *that* unique and specific context which it is in *that* moment facing. That is an action of creation, it is an action that reveals learning. Learning about what is going on, and understanding it.

This was the formal path that we walked in the writing of this dissertation. As a conclusion, and put simply, we could say that in its whole, this dissertation was mainly concerned with mechanistic structures that, in our opinion, seem to wither the process of unfolding of human beings. Nevertheless, and obviously, these structures, systems, etc., are not the sole cause of this atrophy. Something much deeper will be in the root of that problem. The problem being whatever it might be in the very source of violence, the ignorance and the inability to learn, to create anew.

Besides, there is a mutual changeability in this equation: society and its structures affect man — but society and its structures are a reflection of this same man. So, after the long path that we have “walked” in the writing of the present dissertation, we can see that the source of the problem (the tendency to habit, mechanisation, loss of creativity, and sensitivity towards the subtle and flowing reality) is not *in* the structures, themselves. It is not *in* an educational system, in the technology, or globalisation of certain institutions. It is not in these things, *per se*. We consider this an important discovery: it is not in the institutions, organisations, etc. *themselves* — but in the *use* given to them. So the problem is the *way we use* technology, institutions, organisations,

etc. The problem is the way we use whatever it might be, without having an artful, right measure. As a teacher recently told me “we can invent whatever institutions, organisations and structures we want, as long we do not deeply change our character, their use will be destructive”. And this might be the most important point for us to learn.

On this point we think that our work converged into an ethical area. In fact, the crucial question regarding how to deal with such a *progressing machine*, of which we make part, has to be a humanistic, environmental, holistic... — an ethical one. What is the right measure, what is the adequate action? Such a philosophical question will demand a philosophical, creative answer, which means: an answer that comes from the individual.

In fact, discovering a way to learn, to learn how to learn, including learning about ourselves — the place from where all action starts — that would be the greatest discovery. That would be the *metanoia*, *the turning point* beyond what we, in this dissertation, have called the self-centred values and the mechanisation of society, of the individual, and the whole of life. That would, definitely, be the greatest revolution. As Tolstoy puts thus:

There can be only one permanent revolution — a moral one: the regeneration of the inner man. How is this revolution to take place? Nobody knows how it will take place in humanity, but every man feels it clearly in himself. And yet in our world, everybody thinks of changing humanity, and nobody thinks of changing himself. (Tolstoy: 1990: 19)

With such a change of character, one would know how to deal with the *progressing machine*, what organisations to create, or not create — and to which give, or not, one’s co-operation. All in the right measure.

Reaching the inevitable and necessary end of this dissertation, we would like to use this remarkable quotation by Krishnamurti:

So what we are concerned with is not the division between organisation and freedom but whether we can live in this world without division at all. It is division which denies freedom and love, not organisation. When organisation divides, it leads to war. Belief in any form, ideals, however noble and effective, breed division. Organised religion is the cause of division, just like nationality and

power-groups. So be concerned with those things which divide, those things which bring about division between man and man, whether they be individual or collective. The family, the church, and the State bring about such division. What is important is the movement of thought that divides. Thought itself is always divisive, so all action based on idea or an ideology is a division. Thought cultivates prejudice, opinion, judgement. Man in himself, being divided, seeks freedom out of this division. Not being able to find it he hopes to integrate the various divisions, and of course this is not possible. You cannot integrate two prejudices. To live in this world in freedom means to live with love, eschewing every form of division. When there is freedom and love, then this intelligence will act in co-operation, and will also know when not to co-operate. (Krishnamurti: 1982: 236)

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